

THE ATTRACT PROGRAMME

A STRATEGIC PROPOSAL FOR BOOSTING BREAKTHROUGH CO-INNOVATION ON DETECTION AND IMAGING TECHNOLOGIES IN EUROPE-PREPARING THE SCENE IN PHASE 1

ROY PENNINGGS
PABLO TELLO
MARKUS NORDBERG

1

page
03

ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT AIMS

2

page
05

**DETECTION & IMAGING
TECHNOLOGIES AS KEY ENABLERS
FOR BREAKTHROUGH INNOVATION**

3

page
13

ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

4

page
19

**RELATION TO PRINCIPLES OF OPEN
SCIENCE AND OPEN INNOVATION**

5

page
23

CONCEPT AND APPROACH

6

page
36

**PROPOSAL FOR ATTRACT PHASE-2
PROJECT AND THE UP-SCALING
OF THE ATTRACT PROGRAMME**

1

ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT AIMS

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project is a pilot for a new collaboration paradigm based on the 'Open Science, Open Innovation and Open to the World'¹ philosophy, which will boost our chances of transforming frontier science into products, processes and services meeting societal needs. It has three closely interlinked aims:

- 1 | To start streamlining the breakthrough innovation process** by coupling national and pan-European Research Infrastructures (RIs) and their associated communities (i.e. universities, Research and Technology Organisations) to actors that can extract societally relevant and/or commercially interesting innovations from them. These actors – including the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium partners – comprise (1) industry representatives (through EIRMA²) and (2) innovation specialists (through AALTO and ESADE business schools, each with their own SME networks). This streamlined process will be tested and validated through the identification of 170 potential breakthrough technology concepts, which will be steered by the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium toward societally relevant and commercially worthwhile fields of application.
- 2 | To introduce a co-innovation approach** to invite national and pan-European RIs/university actors, RTOs and industry into a process in which the scientific and industrial communities jointly pursue and generate breakthrough innovation in close and equal partnership.
- 3 | To generate potential breakthrough innovation** in a non-linear fashion by identifying the right (combination(s) of) breakthrough technology options that may achieve the desired solution to a Societal Challenge (effectively recombining technical options to achieve the desired societal result). This enables scientific and industrial research groups to better co-ordinate their research efforts.

¹ Chesbrough, H.W. (2003), "Open Innovation: The new imperative for creating and profiting from technology". Boston: Harvard Business School Press (2003). See also: Christensen, Clayton and Raynor, Michael (2003) in "The Innovator's Solution: Creating and Sustaining Successful Growth". Boston: Harvard Business School Press. See also: W. Chan Kim & Renee Mauborgne (2005) in "Blue Ocean Strategy", Harvard Business School Press.

² European Industrial Research Management Association, with a membership of over 100 major companies across different sectors.

2

DETECTION & IMAGING
TECHNOLOGIES AS KEY ENABLERS
FOR BREAKTHROUGH INNOVATION

Various foresight reports by the United Nations³ and the World Economic Forum⁴ as well as recent articles by, for example, the World Technology Evaluation Center⁵ (WTEC) highlight from multiple angles the interdependence of emerging technologies and knowledge convergence needed to explore scientific goals and so-called Societal Mega-Trends. This dynamic relationship gives rise to rapidly evolving applications across industries. It also creates new interdisciplinary spaces for exploring fundamental research, applications, business opportunities and markets. In the Strategic Research Agendas of European Technology Platforms⁶ such as Nanofutures, Photonics21, SusChem, euRobotics, SmartGrids and others, the importance of Detection & Imaging technologies as key enablers for

innovations in their respective sectors can be clearly seen. A recent Frost & Sullivan report also confirms that Detection & Imaging technologies are particularly important enablers for all the converging technological families (see Figures 1 and 2 below). Detection & Imaging technologies also build bridges spanning these families, from sensors to (big) data processing technologies. The report argues that almost all future major scientific advancements, technical applications, commercially worthwhile products or businesses targeting an upcoming Societal Challenge will be enabled by cutting-edge Detection & Imaging technologies. It forecasts that Detection & Imaging technologies will constitute a direct annual market worth over \$100 billion⁷.

Figure 1: Detection & Imaging value chain

³ United Nations, "World Economic and Social Survey 2013 – Global Trends and Challenges to Sustainable Development post-2015", p. 4.

⁴ World Economic Forum, "Deep Shift Technology Tipping Points and Societal Impact – Survey Report 2015", p. 34.

⁵ World Technology Evaluation Center, 2013, "Convergence of Knowledge, Technology, and Society: Beyond Convergence of Nano-Bio-Info-Cognitive Technologies", pp. 225-227. See also: Mihail C. Roco and William S. Bainbridge in: "The New World of Discovery, Invention, and Innovation: Convergence of Knowledge, Technology, and Society", Journal of Nanoparticle Research, Sept. 2013 (taken from abstract: <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11051-013-1946-1>).

⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/index_en.cfm?pg=etp#etps. This site links directly to the websites of the mentioned European Technology Platforms and their respective Strategic Agenda's (under the 'Publications section').

⁷ Frost & Sullivan, "2015 Top Technologies in Sensors & Control (Technical Insights) - Sensors technologies that will have the highest impact in 2015", May 2015, p. 89.

Figure 2: Top 50 Technologies Web

Detection & Imaging technologies impact on almost all major technology areas. (Source: Frost & Sullivan TechVision 2020 Program - Top 50 Technologies).

ADVANCED MANUFACTURING

Advanced Lasers for Manufacturing
Digital Manufacturing
Intelligent Robots
Micro and Nano Manufacturing

MEDICAL DEVICES & IMAGING

Combination Devices
Digital Pathology
Hybrid Imaging Technologies
Medical Robotics
Optical Imaging Technologies
Smart Pills

LIFESCIENCES & BIOTECHNOLOGY

Adult Stem Cells
Biosensing
Genome Sequencing
Nanofluidics & BioNEMS
3D Cell Culture Systems

CLEAN & GREEN TECHNOLOGY

Advanced Energy Storage
Green Buildings
Green Vehicles
Renewable Chemicals
Smart Grid
Thin Film Photovoltaic
2nd Generation Biofuels

SENSORS & AUTOMATION

CBRN Detection Technologies
Energy Harvesting
Smart Sensors
Wireless Sensor Networks

MATERIALS & COATINGS

Algae-based Ingredients
Advanced Filtration
Breathable Antibacteria Coatings
Compostable Packaging
Enzyme Technology
Lightweight Composites
Nanocatalysts
Smart Textiles
Superhydrophobic Coatings

CONVENTIONAL ENERGY

Advanced Hydrocracking
Clean Coal
Enhanced Oil Recovery

INFORMATION & COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

Cloud Computing
Fabric Computing
Long-Term Evolution
Semantic Web
Virtualisation

MICROELECTRONICS

Emerging Data Storage Technologies
Flexible Electronics
Haptics & Touch Technologies
Next Generation Displays
Wireless Power Transmission
3D Integration
LED Lighting Technologies

Here are some examples, based on Figure 2:

- > **Mega-trend: Connectivity & Data Traffic.** By 2020 there will be over 80 billion⁸ connected devices. Users will own and operate at least five connected devices and households will have at least 10. With the advent of the 'Internet of Things', the number of devices with online identities (digital IDs) per km² will skyrocket. The challenge will be: (1) to deal with the exponential increase in data traffic and (2), to take advantage of the data deluge. ERIs already have technologies that can analyse 3200 terabytes of data a year⁹. The question is how to transfer the scientific knowledge to do this to application areas such as energy management, global emergency response, weather forecasting etc.
- > **Mega-trend: Air Mobility.** Between 2009 and 2028, world passenger traffic is forecast to increase 5% per annum¹⁰ and world cargo traffic by 5%. Traffic will nearly triple, and airlines will more than double their fleets. According to Boeing, the commercial fleet will grow from 21,600 aircraft in 2014 to 44,000 aircraft in 2034. The biggest challenge for Europe will be to maintain its technology leadership. One way to do this could be to use opto-electronics sensing technology developed by ERIs for fundamental research to perform real-time monitoring of the technical health status of the airplane. This would cut costs for airlines and enable more efficient maintenance scheduling.
- > **Mega-trend: Zero Emissions.** In 2002, the carbon footprint of data centres worldwide was 76 million metric tonnes of CO₂e¹¹. This is expected to more than triple by 2020, making it the fastest-growing contributor to the ICT sector's carbon footprint. The big challenge is to achieve a zero-emission ICT industry and in doing so help reduce the CO₂e footprint of other industrial sectors. One option is to investigate how the hardware (i.e. micro-cooled ASICs) and software (e.g. cloud computing) technologies currently being developed by different national and pan-European RIs for large instruments can be put to work to reduce the global CO₂e footprint of commercial data centres.
- > **Mega-trend: Personalised Medicine.** The risk of getting cancer is rising as Europe's population ages. Between 2002 and 2012 the number of new cancer cases rose by 20% to 3.4 million a year¹², with an associated cost burden. Chips such as the one developed by the MediPix consortium¹³ are already being applied in X-ray CT, in prototype systems for digital mammography, in CT imagers for mammography and for beta and gamma autoradiography of biological samples. However, if we are to create more personalised treatment options, we need much faster scanners, to check more people more quickly, with better resolution and tumour targeting to improve the identification of tumours.

⁸ The American convention (The short-scale échelle courte) is used throughout for 'billion' (10⁹)

⁹ http://atlasexperiment.org/pdf/fact_sheet_1page.pdf.

¹⁰ Airbus 2009-2028 Global Market Forecast: <http://www.aircargonews.net/news/single-view/news/boeing-ups-aircraft-demand-expectation.html>.

¹¹ Equivalent CO₂ (CO₂e) is the concentration of CO₂ that would cause the same level of radiative forcing as a given type and concentration of greenhouse gas.

¹² Ferlay J, Steliarova-Foucher E, Lortet-Tieulent J, Rosso S, Coebergh JWW, Comber H, Forman D, Bray F in "Cancer incidence and mortality patterns in Europe: estimates for 40 countries in 2012". Eur J Cancer. 2013 Apr;49(6):1374-403. doi: 10.1016/j.ejca.2012.12.027. The mortality rate from cancer is 51% within 5 years. See for details: <http://eco.iarc.fr/EUCAN/Cancer.aspx?Cancer=0>.

¹³ <http://medipix.web.cern.ch/medipix/index.php>.

Figure 3 is an overview of further mega-trends in which Detection & Imaging technologies play a key role:

Figure 3: Main technology trends in Detection & Imaging (Also see Chapter 2 on Impact for a more detailed description). (Source: Frost & Sullivan, Megatrends in Technology Convergence).

The ATTRACT Programme has been developed against the backdrop of the aforementioned reports. It starts with a seed-funding mechanism (ATTRACT Phase-1 Project) to identify a wide range of Detection & Imaging technologies (Technology Readiness Levels 2-4) with breakthrough potential. It is planned to follow with a scale-funding approach (ATTRACT Phase-2 Project) in terms of industrial scalability (toward TRL 5-8) to create social added value¹⁴. The ATTRACT Programme (building upon the Phase 1 and Phase 2 Projects), will create an

ecosystem within which Europe’s leading national and pan-European RIs and their associated user communities, RTOs, large and small industry, and the private investor communities can co-operate to turn curiosity-driven, frontier research efforts into new products, processes and services. The phased deployment of the ATTRACT Programme will spark a new wave of young entrepreneurs, small ventures and innovative services that can support growth and jobs for years to come.

Business and innovation experts

Private and public funding

European Commission

Research Infrastructures

Industry

Figure 4: Illustration of the ATTRACT Programme Co-Innovation model showing the inter-relationship and interdependence of scientific research groups in RIs, RTOs business innovation experts, industry.

¹⁴ The ATTRACT Consortium has established a dialogue with the EC for a potential phase 2 within Horizon 2020.

The ATTRACT Programme will create a sustainable innovation ecosystem by repeating the seed-funding and scale-up stages of the ATTRACT Phase-1 and Phase-2 Projects¹⁵, and adding further mechanisms to help breakthrough research turn into breakthrough innovations. This proposal represents the first phase of that cycle, in which an independent committee¹⁶ of top-level experts in Detection & Imaging technologies identifies high-risk scientific ideas, concepts and technologies that may have breakthrough innovation potential. Funding from H2020 is needed to kick-start this process of co-innovation (see below for explanation of the concept). The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project is shown as the grey part in Figure 5 below.

Once the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project has proven itself by identifying, selecting and guiding 170 high-potential technology concepts, the **second phase in the innovation cycle** (e.g. ATTRACT Phase-2 Project; not funded by this Call) will launch a scale-funding mechanism so that Europe's academic research communities, large and small companies and private investor groups can hone these technologies and take their outcomes to market.

The envisioned ATTRACT Phase-2 Project is shown in yellow in Figure 5 below.

The ATTRACT Phase-2 Project is mentioned here because it is considered key to furthering selection of the most promising breakthrough concepts funded by the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project on the path to market (moving project concepts from TRL 2-4 up to TRL 5-8 and therefore for the success of the ATTRACT Programme model. By using a dedicated selection procedure targeting scientific excellence and innovation potential with careful project monitoring, the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project will create a pipeline of projects that are well qualified for further development and funding in the second phase. The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium has already done much of the groundwork for this through (among other actions) several investor community meetings in London, successful technology scoping exercises in Barcelona and Strasbourg (see section 1.5 and Annex 1 for details) and a symposium at AALTO University in Finland on how to engage with the innovation expert communities.

¹⁵ The ATTRACT Programme is envisioned by the Consortium in the next Framework Programme FPg; initial discussions are taking place with the EC.

¹⁶ Later in this proposal, this independent committee is referred to as the "RDI Committee" or the "IC". Its specific role is outlined later in the document.

Figure 5: This Figure illustrates ATTRACT Phase-1 and Phase-2 Projects. The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project is a seed-funding mechanism for the identification of high-risk, high-gain technologies to bring them up towards TRL 4 and above. In a continuous and structured manner, the envisioned ATTRACT Phase-2 Project will create societal and economic value from the scientific ideas and technologies of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project using public funding to the point where it becomes a financially sustainable/acceptable risk for private investment communities.

The proposed ATTRACT Phase-1 Project goes far beyond creating a spin-out machine for specific technologies. It is a seed-funding mechanism for innovation fit for 21st century needs. By sustaining the research and development of highly promising technologies from ATTRACT Phase-1 into ATTRACT Phase-2, the ATTRACT Programme will bring together entrepreneurs, scientists, engineers, investors and cross-disciplinary innovation and entrepreneurship students to jointly develop specialised technologies to find new ways of solving economic and social problems. Can we use sensors to help the visually impaired navigate the world more easily? Can we develop better forms of on-line learning? Can we pioneer ways to monitor our changing climate more accurately and cost effectively – and develop strategies to mitigate the damage? Answering these questions requires an open, sharing attitude from the outset, so breakthrough innovation concepts can be rapidly identified, assessed, industrially scaled or rejected by various experts along the innovation value chain exploring them at once. As the ideas move towards a real product or service, it is vital that their value is captured for scientists, innovators, their investors, the economy and society.

3

ATTRACT PHASE-1
PROJECT OBJECTIVES

THE OVERALL ATTRACT PHASE -1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES ARE AS FOLLOWS:

- 1 | It will become an **open and inclusive platform**, creating the next generation of Detection & Imaging technologies rooted in ground-breaking, fundamental science use with anticipated applications in the fields of medicine, manufacturing industry, aerospace, ICT, engineering and beyond. It will bring together the existing innovation potential, know-how and expertise of national and pan-European RIs and their associated user communities, industry (large corporations and specialised SMEs) and Innovation and Business organisations.
- 2 | It will embrace one of the key lessons of innovation: radical technology development is based on the premise of 'high-risk/high-pay-off', and a tolerance of, and rapid learning from, failure if some developments turn out to have a less-than-expected market potential (directly or embedded) or fail on scientific grounds. The critical point is that the decision to continue, adapt or end a development can be taken quickly, so that scientific capacity and/or financial investment can be diverted if necessary. The Project will take the first important step toward parallelisation and rapid assessment of potential win-win (industry-science) opportunities to enable better and faster forecasting of the prospects of success for all sides, leading to faster time-to-science & market (see Figure 6).
- 3 | The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project 'Final Assessment Conference' will present the breakthrough technology potential of the 170 funded technology concepts and by fostering relationships with private investors (already on-going), trigger the interest of private capital.
- 4 | The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project thus becomes the vehicle for scientific and industrial research groups and private investors in the multiple application fields to decide which concepts to move further up the TRL ladder. This will be of critical importance for fostering and strengthening fast innovating (micro)-SMEs as well as for channelling projects with the potential for rapid scaling to large firms.

Figure 6: The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project will be the first major step in an iterative cycle in a much faster technology development pathway that will result in a faster time-to-science & market for new breakthrough innovations.

THE ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES ARE TO:

- 1 |** Identify a minimum of 170 breakthrough concepts or technologies (TRL 2-4) in the domain of Detection & Imaging technologies across Europe with the aim of boosting job creation in the EU Member States and Associated Countries.
- 2 |** Assess, through peer review by an Independent RDI [Research, Development, Innovation] Committee (hereafter referred to as the 'IC') from within the domain, the technical feasibility and innovation potential of the identified opportunities.
- 3 |** Fund 170 expert-evaluated breakthrough opportunities/concepts (each receiving €100,000 of seed funding) toward the development of a proof-of-concept or prototype while keeping in mind applications beyond fundamental research.
- 4 |** Guide the funded opportunities by providing technical and business concept advice toward conversion to breakthrough innovations by using the expertise of top-level independent technical experts from the IC and Europe's leading business schools and who are members of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium.
- 5 |** Initiate and promote a mechanism to capture the interest of private investors (Business Angels, Venture Capital firms, corporates) to facilitate the leverage of private capital out of public funding.
- 6 |** Select and – if relevant and possible - cluster opportunities with a clear potential for successful industrial implementation (transition towards private investment market).
- 7 |** Strongly contribute to the achievement of a more evenly spread European Innovation Area in which researchers, scientific knowledge and technology circulate more freely.

The 'Open Science to Open Innovation' approach of the ATTRACT Programme and its link with young entrepreneurs was discussed in a symposium held at AALTO University¹⁷ in Espoo (September 2016). There, it was confirmed that at present, the training of students at many RIs does not include interdisciplinary and entrepreneurship elements; students tend to carry out a pre-specified set of tasks with little scope for communication with fellow students working on other projects. The symposium investigated novel ways to bridge/link basic and frontier research to more applied Design Thinking philosophies¹⁸ and similar methodologies taught in MSc programmes¹⁹ and in companies such as IBM, SAP and IDEO²⁰, where technologies are 'just' a functional way to solving an identified real-world need. The thought behind this is that this link will also significantly contribute toward a more evenly spread European Innovation Area.

The result of this symposium was to add another objective for the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project, which is to run a pilot programme with young MSc interdisciplinary student teams based on Design Thinking methodologies. The pilot programme will be inspired by the breakthrough technologies and innovations funded in the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project. The purpose of this pilot is to:

- 1 |** Use Design Thinking methodologies to extract social value directly from the fundamental science realm.
- 2 |** Demonstrate how an entrepreneurship and co-creation mind-set could be instilled in novel ways to pursue social benefit.
- 3 |** Complement the current training methods of MSc students in RIs in novel ways.
- 4 |** Analyse the lessons learned in this pilot for the scale-up in the ATTRACT Phase-2 Project and the ATTRACT Programme.

THE OUTCOMES OF THE ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT WILL BE:

- > **A bigger economic and societal return on Europe's scientific investment into national and pan-European RIs;**
- > Proof of the effectiveness of the new paradigm as a mechanism for developing radical technologies created in the service of science into breakthrough innovations with industrial relevance and high societal value;
- > A mechanism to prequalify early-stage technology developments for scale funding, by delivering a fast and rigorous assessment tool for making smart selections of breakthrough technology concepts and converting them into breakthrough innovation, so that private investment communities can then decide on industrial scalability, potential market value and therefore investment;
- > A significant contribution toward the establishment of a new generation of interdisciplinary scientists, engineers and innovative entrepreneurs, who are inspired by Design Thinking²¹ to create socially valuable innovation out of instrumentation that was developed for implementation of RIs' scientific missions;
- > A significant contribution to a scientific culture of Open Science and Open Innovation across Europe.

²¹ See e.g. T. Brown, Change By Design, Harper-Collins (2009); M.G. Luchs, K.S. Swan, A. Griffin (eds.) in "Design Thinking", Wiley (2016).

Table 1 below shows the expected benefits from participation in ATTRACT Phase-1 Project for each kind of stakeholder.

BENEFITS	
Research Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to complementary industrial talent, know-how and industrial manufacturing capability. - New opportunities to further develop and speed-up technology upgrading programmes. - Seed long term collaborative links with industry. - Opportunity to learn and apply Design-Thinking methodologies.
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to a unique network of know-how and talent in national and pan-European RIs and their scientific user communities. - Contributing as co-developers (not just as 'old school' sub-contractors). - Access to new industry networks via other projects funded through ATTRACT Phase-1 Project. - Lower costs and shorter time to market for developing breakthrough applications. - Development of new applications for new markets.
Private Investment Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A structured mechanism for learning about potential breakthrough technologies in RIs. - Early identification of potential innovation investment options for technologies coming out of RIs. - Structured platform for interaction with RIs and industry toward joint development of breakthrough technology.
Young entrepreneurs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunity to learn about potential breakthrough technologies in RIs and apply modern skills (e.g. Design Thinking) to create novel, societally relevant ideas for future market applications. - Access to a unique network of scientific user communities. - A platform for interaction with Private Investment Communities and industry collaborations.

Table 1: The main benefits that ATTRACT Phase-1 Project will bring to industry, the Detection & Imaging research communities, and potential private investors and young entrepreneurs.

4

RELATION TO PRINCIPLES
OF OPEN SCIENCE
AND OPEN INNOVATION

This ATTRACT Phase-1 Project is submitted as a result of a three-year process of engaging in iterative discussions between some of Europe's leading RIs, some large industry players and several private investment communities with close ties to niche SMEs²². A special ATTRACT website (<https://attract-eu.com/>) was created to provide the various stakeholders with information about the Programme and its two Phases, and to help them take part in round-tables. These discussions revealed that both industry and investors regard RIs as providers of leading-edge technologies with high innovation potential but that the design and development of components, instruments, services and knowledge is not always sufficiently exploited to improve existing applied technologies. In many cases, the knowledge and innovation potential that could have been harnessed by industry have not been used or valued sufficiently by RIs to speed up development. Furthermore, too little attention has been paid to applying jointly-developed technology in novel, highly advanced market applications.

This issue has also been investigated by Prof. Henry Chesbrough of the University of Berkeley and ESADE in his influential work on moving from Open Science to Open Innovation²³. Chesbrough, through his advisory role in the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Advisory Committee (PAC), has greatly helped the Consortium to strengthen this link. To confirm that there really is an unmet need, the ATTRACT Programme Consortium (which is the same as the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium Board) undertook two preliminary scoutings of breakthrough research projects. The first two-day 'Technology Trends, Wishes and Dreams' (TWD) Symposium on Detection & Imaging Technologies, held at ESADE in Barcelona in June 2016, was a big success: 80 breakthrough technology project concepts were presented²⁴ from across the Detection & Imaging community. Over 180 scientists, industry researchers and interested private investment parties attended this event (see Figure 7 for an impression of the meeting). Due to over-subscription, a second scouting symposium was held in Strasbourg in November 2016 and led to the presentation of 22 additional concepts and attendance by a further 72 participants²⁵.

²² The ATTRACT Programme Consortium participated in several Global Corporate Venturing conferences to test the model against the needs of corporate and private investors. See: <http://www.eventbrite.co.uk/o/global-corporate-venturing-mawsonia-ltd-5408982681>.

²³ For his most recent publication, see: <http://www.sciencebusiness.net/eventsarchive/OpenScience/OpenScience.pdf>. This paper provides the theoretical basis for the ATTRACT model.

²⁴ See for details: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/470460/>. Details of a selection of the presented project concepts are shown also in Annex 1 of this proposal.

²⁵ See for details: <http://indico.cern.ch/event/542659/>.

Figure 7: Pictures taken during the two first 'Technology Trends, Wishes and Dreams' (TWD) Symposia on Detection & Imaging Technologies in Barcelona (June 2016) and Strasbourg (November 2016).

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project is an essential part of the envisioned ATTRACT Programme's co-innovation paradigm for implementing the transition from Open Science towards Open Innovation²⁶. Both the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project and the ATTRACT Programme as a whole can thus be placed in the top-right Pasteur Quadrant

(see Figure 8 below). The Pasteur Quadrant²⁷ is a classification of scientific research projects or initiatives that seek fundamental understanding of scientific problems, while also being of immediate use for society. It distinguishes various perspectives within science, engineering and technology.

Figure 8: The co-innovation paradigm as proposed by the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project and the wider envisioned ATTRACT Programme fits in the top right Pasteur Quadrant.

²⁶ H.W. Chesbrough, "From Open Science to Open Innovation", ESADE Working paper, Science|Business Publishing 2015.

²⁷ Stokes, Donald E. in "Pasteur's Quadrant – Basic Science and Technological Innovation", Brookings Institution Press (1997) p. 196.

CONCEPT AND APPROACH

CONCEPT

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium strongly believes that societal problems cannot be solved using incrementally improved technologies developed in competition by different research groups²⁸. This is because such an approach leaves group collaboration in pursuit of a breakthrough solution largely to chance. Furthermore, this approach is very time-consuming, expensive and does not foster co-ordination of and synergy in publicly-funded research programmes. This model also makes it difficult for companies and investors to take informed decisions on which technologies to back, thus leaving worthwhile projects unfunded.

As outlined in Section 1.1, the ATTRACT Programme's vision is that:

- 1 |** The pursuit of fundamental science is uniquely placed to lead to breakthrough technologies.
- 2 |** When these breakthrough technologies arise through co-innovation (i.e. pursuing win-win opportunities) between research communities and industry, they can generate societal value more quickly and efficiently, saving costs, research capacity and resources.

This vision will be implemented through Open Innovation, which emphasises partnering for mutual advantage and access to skills and resources one would otherwise have to develop by oneself. Open Innovation also allows for failures in technology development, as radical ideas can be tried and tested faster. An ecosystem based on Open Innovation will help industry to identify which breakthrough technologies needed for frontier research have market potential. The ATTRACT Programme's success should be measured in terms of:

- > Increased returns on investments into European RIs.
- > Enhanced use of RI capacity and technology by industry.
- > More private investment in high-gain technology as the ATTRACT Programme effectively 'de-risks' part of the technology development.
- > Greater research mobility between and across scientific and industrial research groups.
- > Better harnessing of cross-disciplinary student innovation potential in universities and business schools, resulting in an overall strengthening of the European Research Area.

²⁸ See: S Singh in "New Mega Trends Implications for our Future Lives", Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2012. See also: B. Schneiderman in "Science 2.0". Science, March 2008, vol.319, pp. 1349-1350.

REASONS FOR THE THIRD-PARTY REDISTRIBUTION MECHANISM

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Consortium members find the Third-Party redistribution mechanism offered by the EC an excellent instrument for:

- > Ensuring future availability of Detection and Imaging technologies for the purpose of supporting RIs' future technology upgrading programmes, leading to key advances in fundamental science.
- > Establishing better connection and synergies between national and pan-European RIs and their associated research communities.
- > Increasing the visibility of the pan-European RIs to scientific research communities that have so far not been engaged or even been aware of the potential that pan-European RIs have to offer in terms of basic scientific instrumentation.
- > Continuing to attract young research talent across and beyond Europe.
- > Supporting the sustainability of SMEs so they can continue to develop, manufacture and deliver the necessary instrumentation needed for basic research.

APPROACH

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project will act as a seed funder for 170²⁹ carefully selected technology concepts, cascading €17 million (out of the €20 million requested H2020 funding) through an Open Call to RI-academia-RTO-industry consortia. It will distribute the funding to successful proposals as a lump sum of €100,000 at the start of each of the projects. The reason for allocating €100,000 per funded project is that:

- 1 | This amount allows a larger geographical reach of public funding across the EU Member States and Associated Countries.
- 2 | It spreads available EU funding more evenly between large companies and SMEs.
- 3 | It facilitates the entry of new participants or non-experienced organisations in European funding programmes (i.e. small universities and polytechnics, recently created SMEs etc.).
- 4 | The time for implementing the selected ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call projects is 12 months; the amount is balanced against the time the projects have to develop a conceptual prototype.

²⁹ Since the European Commission Call text clearly specifies that the financial support to Third-Parties is the primary aim of the Action, the number of 170 fundable projects has been established as a result of maximising Third-Party funding and allocating sufficient resources for the management of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project.

FINANCIAL ASPECTS BEARING ON IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT SEED-FUNDING MECHANISM

- 1 |** The seed-funding mechanism will entail the lump sum payment of €100,000 to each selected project consortia (e.g. Third-Parties), with a maximum of 170 funded projects.
- 2 |** Funding is provided after successful conclusion of a Third-Party Agreement (TPPA).
- 3 |** Each funded project will last one year after the TPPA has been signed.
- 4 |** The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium will report on technical and financial progress to the EC, in line with standard requirements of the H2020 R&I Work Programme (see above).

THE PROCESS FOR THE ATTRACT PHASE-1 OPEN CALL

The bodies in charge are: the Project Consortium Board (PCB; highest decision-making authority); the Independent RDI Committee (IC); the Project Advisory Committee (PAC; committee linking the ATTRACT Programme to corporate and private investment interest); the Project Administrative Office (PAO; day-to-day project implementation office). Their composition, roles and responsibilities are described in Section 1.6.

1 | Identification of ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call themes

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Open Call will be challenge-driven, bottom-up and cover Detection & Imaging technologies, categorised as: sensors,

front and back end electronics, data acquisition systems and computing, software and integration. The Open Call will focus solely on identifying breakthrough challenges. These themes are a standard classification recognised by the RI and Industrial communities in Europe. This process is led by the IC. The IC will include top-level researchers from the domain of Detection & Imaging, specialists from potential user-communities as well as potential industry users of the technology. The IC is independent from the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium (i.e. Consortium partners are not part of the IC, to guarantee that the funding decisions are decoupled from the Consortium). The administrative and logistic process of implementing the Open Call process is handled by the PAO.

2 | Publication and management of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call application process

Organising and managing the Open Call is the responsibility of the PAO, which has a logistic and administrative role. To raise awareness of the Open Call among the various research communities (national RIs, academic centres, Research & Technology Organisations (RTOs), corporate industry and specialised SMEs), the PAO will work closely with the Phase-1 Project Consortium's Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) and also use several other channels, such as the ATTRACT website. This approach has been tested with great success in the aforementioned 'Technology Trends, Wishes and Dreams' (TWD) Symposia on Detection & Imaging Technologies in Barcelona and Strasbourg. EC communication channels (see WP6 for details) including the EC Participant Portal and the EU*Research Focus/Results Magazines will be used to create the widest possible awareness among researchers of the funding scheme.

Together with the Open Call publication, the PAO will publish all necessary supporting documentation for potential applicants and an FAQ based on questions that arise from interested parties. This includes the evaluation criteria that will be used by the IC (see below for details). The PAO will also provide and manage the electronic submission process set up for the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project and offer an online helpdesk. Proposals will be limited to 4 pages (excluding the title page and public summary), with clear guidelines on the structure of the proposal given in the supporting documentation. The proposal application sections are as follows:

The Call will remain open to applicants for three months. Once the Call is closed, the proposals will be forwarded to the IC for evaluation and selection. Upon request from the IC Chair, the PAO will provide administrative support services to the IC members carrying out the evaluation and selection.

- 1|** Project public summary (max. 3000 characters).
- 2|** Project description (describing the objectives).
- 3|** Technology benchmark (describing how the technology developed in the project compares to existing technologies).
- 4|** Envisioned innovation potential (describing how the innovation potential (scientific and/or industrial) is seen on a time horizon within the next decade. It should also describe how such envisioned potential could benefit European society and their citizens).
- 5|** Project implementation, budget breakdown and final deliverables (describing how the project will be implemented (steps) within the course of its twelve-month duration. An indicative budget breakdown (personal costs, travel, equipment, other...) will be provided for €100 k funding. A table will be included of expected results after twelve months of work.

Special attention shall be paid to the deliverables to ensure proper public dissemination of the project results). Open sharing of project information and deliverables is encouraged among all applicants. At the very least, applicants must undertake to provide public dissemination for the following deliverables at the ATTRACT Final Assessment Conference in Brussels:

- A|** A final project summary in PDF format running to no more than 2000 characters, including spaces.
- B|** A poster presentation (format to be announced no later than two months before the ATTRACT Final Assessment Conference).
- C|** A 'scientific journal-type' article summarising the main project results and methodology used to achieve them.

3 | Selection of proposals to be funded

The IC is an independent body; it will not include any ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium partners, to demonstrate a complete decoupling between the management of the seed-funding programme and the evaluation and selection of individual projects. It comprises top scientific and industrial experts in Detection & Imaging technologies and leading representatives of private investment communities. After careful assessment (maximum three months after the Open Call is closed) the IC will evaluate the submitted proposals, draw up a ranking list and specify which ones should be funded. The assessment criteria for the IC are as follows (in line with the proposal template structure above), with a weighted score per section:

The IC's ranking list and funding recommendation is forwarded to the PCB, which will verify and confirm in their meeting that the evaluation process has been carried out transparently and in accordance with EC Appendix K of the Work Programme. The names of the IC members will be published on the ATTRACT website when the Open Call process is launched as a proof of the IC's top scientific, industrial and investment innovation quality, adding to the transparency of the process. As shown above, the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project intends to launch a single Open Call. In the unlikely event that the response is lower than 500 and/or does not generate 170 IC-selected high potential concepts, an additional Open Call may be launched one month later.

- 1 | Are the project proposal objectives adequately and clearly defined?
- 2 | Are the project proposal objectives adequately and clearly explained?
- 3 | Is the technology proposed for development clearly an advance on the state of the art?
- 4 | Will the scientific use increase knowledge in the scientific discipline(s) mentioned?
- 5 | Will the expected advances have the potential to contribute to improved or new industrial applications?
- 6 | Will the potential scientific and/or industrial applications benefit European society and citizens?
- 7 | Are the project implementation steps fully explained?
- 8 | Do the proposed implementation steps show that the anticipated results are achievable within twelve months?
- 9 | Does the budget breakdown correspond to the presented implementation steps and is it reasonable?
- 10 | Does the proposal support openness?

4 | Post-selection process

After confirmation by the PCB, the PAO will publish the evaluation results of the selected applicants, send personal notifications to the Third-Parties and commence the funding contract process with successful applicants, based on the ATTRACT TPPA and a single lump sum payment of €100,000 per funded project. The contracting process is expected to be completed within one month. It should be noted that the TPPA is a standard contract whose provisions are not open to individual negotiations between the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project PCB and the selected Open Call applicants. This ensures equal treatment of all ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call applicants and a timely conclusion of the TPPAs.

Funded projects will have one year to produce their results (also called 'deliverables'). The PAO will ensure the administrative follow-up and that scientific and technical progress is monitored for each project. The PAO will not interfere in the way the allocated funding is spent to achieve the project's aim. In close collaboration with the IC, WP5 will be responsible for the scientific and technical monitoring of funded projects and provide (some) advice, guidance or network access if requested and agreed by the PCB. WP5 will not interfere, delay or stop ongoing projects but will refer any significant deviations encountered via the PAO to the PCB for further action. During the year, business and innovation experts from the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium's leading university (AALTO) and business school (ESADE), will provide assistance (in the form of guidance or coaching, depending on requirement) to the projects to help them understand

how the breakthrough technology might be transformed into breakthrough innovations with high market relevance and potential. This does not mean that ATTRACT aims to turn research scientists and technology developers for leading-edge science into entrepreneurs for it is generally so that they would have taken other career paths if they had wanted to be entrepreneurs/businessmen. The training support will focus on showing these scientists: (1) how business works, (2) providing them with introductory business knowledge so they can better assess the market potential of their technology (3) making the researchers effective partners in business processes and (4) smoothing the path for those researchers interested in becoming entrepreneurs.

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project operational concept is summarised in Figure 9 below:

Figure 9: Summary of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project funding mechanism.

5 | End of project

One year after the start of the funded projects, each team will be asked to present its technical results and an initial business concept at the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Final Assessment Conference. The IC will judge each presentation on technical excellence as well as on societal relevance, technological development potential and scope for commercial exploitation. The Final Assessment Conference will enable the invited corporate and private investment communities to recognise projects with the potential for further up-scaling to higher TRLs.

After preparation by the PAO with support of the IC and PAC, the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project PCB will submit a full and detailed report on the evaluation of this seed-funding mechanism to the EC, with options for sustaining the seed-funding programme and further up-scaling of breakthrough innovations³⁰.

Private investors may wish to participate during the development of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call proposals or the execution of the funded projects following ATTRACT Phase-1. Private investors can enter the ATTRACT Programme’s innovation cycle at various points (e.g. in either or both Phases, although it will be rather unlikely in ATTRACT Phase-1), depending on their profile (corporate investor, venture capitalist, Business Angel) since the purpose of the ATTRACT Programme is to move breakthrough technology concepts quickly up the TRL ladder. The funding mechanism in ATTRACT Phase-2 will allow various forms of investment, on a project level, in an SME participating in a project, or as a corporate investment. Figure 10 below shows some of these entry points for potential investors:

Figure 10: The envisioned ATTRACT Programme allows entry points for private investment (e.g. Business Angels, Venture Capital, corporate investment etc.) at any stage following the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project. This Figure does not specifically take into account other forms of engagement such as gifts, or funding a sub-contractor making a vital part.

³⁰ As mentioned in the main text, the envisioned ATTRACT Phase 2 (within H2020) and the ATTRACT Programme (FP9).

PROCESS

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project will operate through six interlinked Work Packages (WPs), and one Project Management WP. Figure 11 below shows the work packages, after which the activities of WPs 2-7 are summarised.

Figure 11: Overview of interlinked WPs for organising, funding and managing the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call.

WPs 2 and 3 each focus on a specific target audience for the identification of technology ideas that may have breakthrough societal and industrial potential. These target groups are:

- WP2: large industry; SMEs and private investment communities, including venture-capital firms, Business Angels;
- WP3: European and national RIs, academic centres and RTOs through their TTO offices.

Each of these WPs will frame messages for their audience and use existing networks to promote participation in the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call. It is clear that there will be overlaps and synergies between these audiences. This is unavoidable, as some industries also have strategic investment objectives, some academic organisations have SME spin-out targets and RIs will already work with industry and SMEs in technology development. This means that the WPs will closely co-ordinate the types and content of communications and the approach to specific audiences. Each WP will – from their target audience – help WP6 provide speakers and specialists to support

dissemination events and local, regional and global outreach activities as well as communications to national research policy makers. The WPs will also provide input to WP7 on the criteria to determine from each of the target audiences whether ATTRACT – as a Programme – is successful in identifying and promoting high-risk scientific ideas toward a TRL that makes them alluring for industry and investors. The input will help to streamline the approach to move projects further up the TRL ladder.

WP4 will run the ‘Young Innovator & Entrepreneurs’ Pilot’ in which MSc students will be encouraged to use Design Thinking methodologies to imagine and develop new societally relevant product or service concepts based on a selection of various technologies featured in the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call funded projects. WP4 will also deliver the dissemination and outreach activities for the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project and will furnish scientists in the 170 ATTRACT Phase-1 funded projects with a basic knowledge/ better grasp of entrepreneurship.

WP5 will focus on monitoring the scientific and technical progress and output of the awarded projects. If irregularities in the execution of awarded projects are found, WP5 will inform the PCB via the PAO.

WP6. The outreach and dissemination activities differ from the work already mentioned to encourage various target audiences to participate in the Open Call. WP6 will inform and promote the results of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project as a highly efficient platform for exploring breakthrough ideas that would otherwise not undergo further development. WP6 will also provide support to those funded Open Call project consortia members who might be interested in becoming future entrepreneurs and/or want expertise on how to further scale up their technology to higher TRLs. This will be done through training in making investment pitches to prepare them for future meetings with private or corporate investors interested in taking breakthrough technologies to market. These training sessions will focus on the acquisition of skills, techniques and ideas that effectively convey what participants' projects/technologies have to offer. Outreach activities at local, regional and national level will take place (through existing outreach programmes by the Phase-1 Project Consortium partners) to help businesses and policy makers grasp how industrial participation in the Open Call and the transfer of knowledge can boost regional and national economic growth and what the focus should/could be in national research agendas to further strengthen regional specialisation.

WP7 will evaluate and validate the results of ATTRACT Phase-1 Project as a model for continuous co-innovation of high-risk breakthrough project concepts. It will draw up the (periodic) evaluation reports from WP2, WP3, WP5 and WP6 and use the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) from WPs 2-3 and the assessments from the IC and the PAC as well as the ATTRACT Phase-1 Consortium's Project PCB and external stakeholders to (further) refine the model toward sustainability (for example, moving the funded projects higher up the TRL ladder). WP7 will also provide insight on how the ATTRACT Phase-1 model (and even the Programme) could be transferred to other science domains.

Figure 12 below shows the timeline of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project activities. The launch of the Open Call right at the start is an option. This is because the Consortium members discussed all aspects of the Open Call implementation in detail as part of the development of the H2020 ATTRACT Phase-1 proposal. As part of their commitment and In Kind Contribution (IKC), the following preparatory implementation actions with regards to the Open Call have therefore already been defined, agreed and/or developed:

- > Draft templates for proposal submission and evaluation criteria and guidelines.
- > The content and legal consistency of the TPPAs.
- > The online proposal submission system.

Figure 12: Overall timeline of project activities. Original proposal.

6

PROPOSAL FOR ATTRACT PHASE-2
PROJECT AND THE UP-SCALING
OF THE ATTRACT PROGRAMME

To create breakthrough innovations that have a real impact on the many societal issues that face us globally, radical ideas must be given time to gestate and be tried in a setting in which risks can be taken and risk entertained. The ATTRACT Programme Consortium expects that no more than 4-to-6 out of every 100 ideas submitted in the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call will have the potential to transform society. As discussed earlier, it is out of the small number of really potent ideas that large societal and economic benefits arise. ATTRACT Phase-1 can be seen as a way of fishing these ideas out of a deep pool.

The scientists (academic and industrial scientists alike) who create these breakthrough ideas will mostly be engaged in basic science projects and will use ATTRACT Phase-1 as a means to test a novel idea and whether it could also have other uses. It is important to understand that the end-results of ATTRACT Phase-1 funded projects are still a long way from the market. What the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project does is start a cycle that will cut the time to create and develop a technology by up to 50% compared with traditional pathways (see Figure 13 below). In other words: the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project absorbs initial (industrial) investment risk to try unproven tracks that might lead to the next big innovation.

Figure 13: One can explore, test, and validate the market potential for specific applications much faster by building on technologies originally developed for fundamental science projects. This will slash internal and external development costs for companies and allow a faster time-to-market. In particular, SMEs will benefit by reducing the need for costly in-house research.

The ATTRACT Phase-1 Project alone will generate a set of technology results that will have moved from a 'wild idea' to a validated technology proposition, but whose market applicability is still largely unclear. It is unlikely that an industrial or private investor would already be prepared to assume the financial risk to up-scale these ideas or prototypes, given their - still - very speculative nature and potential. Investors will also know that although it will still be the same scientists who will have to lead up-scaling work, they are unlikely to be interested in (or necessarily good at) moving the technology to the point where a more traditional product development cycle can be started.

Another step is needed for radical ideas that make it through the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project process and put them on the path towards real world, products and services relevant to society. This is what we call the envisioned ATTRACT Phase-2 Project (which is not the subject of this proposal). It centres on a stepwise reduction of investment risk as the identified technologies move higher up the TRL-ladder (TRL 5-8), revealing potentially valuable applications. As the technology moves up this ladder, the clearer it will become where interesting applications might develop. This is the stage at which point investors will start to create professional eco-systems to capture the value of these ideas.

The ATTRACT Phase-2 Project can be summarised as a public financial instrument allowing radical technologies to develop into future innovations which address key societal needs. It enables ideas developed in the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project to withstand the pressure of having to compete immediately with other – faster but also more incrementally oriented – investment projects. The ATTRACT Phase-2 Project is a specific approach to bridging the so-called 'Valley of Death' for breakthrough technologies that – by their very nature – need more time to come to fruition.

The ATTRACT Phase-2 Project is currently seen by the ATTRACT Programme Consortium as a further proposal to be submitted under the H2020 2018-2020 Work Programme, where it would provide the financial up-scaling mechanism to some 6-8 validated ATTRACT Phase-1 Project technologies.

There are plenty of modern-day applications (see Table 2 below) that offer evidence how RI-generated technology has found its way into our society. Some examples are listed in the table below. As has been argued from the start of this proposal, this transition has taken place by pure chance, not through a systematic approach. The true value of the whole proposed ATTRACT Programme therefore lies in the intrinsic synergy of ATTRACT Phase-1 and ATTRACT Phase-2. Here, partners in the ATTRACT

Programme Consortium have modelled its global potential. **Their simulations suggest that over a period of ten years, nurturing and supporting up to 600 radical science-driven innovation projects in ATTRACT (within a budget envelope of €2 billion of public and private funding) would achieve an economic multiplication factor of 10 or more.**

Table 2: Examples of modern-day applications that originate from RI technology developed for fundamental science projects.

Some modern-day applications <i>(not specifically selected for Societal Need, but to demonstrate the relationship with RI technology development)</i>	Originating RI technology for fundamental science projects
A quarter of the world's 20 most-used drugs were developed using synchrotrons. Examples: malaria, flu and AIDS treatments.	Synchrotron research.
Over 20,000 MRI scanners used in hospitals around the world.	Superconducting cable (multi-cored Rutherford cable) for use in high field magnets for particle physics experiments (e.g. the Delphi and H1 solenoids).
Cordless vacuum cleaners.	Portable, self-contained drill capable of extracting core samples from below the lunar surface (NASA project, developed by Black & Decker).
Detection of bed bugs in hotel bedrooms.	Analysis of gases on the comet 69P/Churyumov-Gerasimenko.
'Bionic Ear' (cochlear implant).	Development of electronic sensing systems, telemetry, sounds and vibrations sensors in the Space Shuttle programme.
Wireless communication (WiFi).	Australian astronomers studying radiation from Black Holes.
Modern Bio-Pharma industry (estimate: for every \$1 public investment, the return has been \$141 in the economy ³¹).	The Human Genome project.
World Wide Web.	Automatic information-sharing between scientists in universities and institutes around the world.

³¹ http://www.battelle.org/docs/default-document-library/economic_impact_of_the_human_genome_project.pdf.

The envisioned ATTRACT Programme will involve multiple iterations of the ATTRACT Phase-1 and ATTRACT Phase-2 Projects, to enable a continuous cycle of selecting and nurturing breakthrough science, and facilitating the development of its results into breakthrough innovations. Within the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project, WP7 will produce a final report on the envisioned structure and mechanisms for the ATTRACT Programme. Although it is hard to say what they are now, the Consortium can outline some of the key initial ingredients that the ATTRACT Programme may contain:

- > The notion of co-innovation as a mechanism to balance collaboration and competition.
- > The paradigm from ‘Open Science to Open Innovation and Open to the World’ as the overarching concept.
- > The synergy of public funding with private funding to absorb and mitigate the risks that breakthrough technologies face as they progress towards the market.

Identifying the conceptual and operational backbone of the envisioned ATTRACT Programme could lead to a sustainable ecosystem model applicable to other technology realms beyond Detection and Imaging (see Figure 14 below).

For Europe, the successful implementation and continuation of the ATTRACT Programme will result in greater synergy and return on their investment in the 600+ national and pan-European RI infrastructures (€2,488 billion under Horizon 2020, multiplied many-fold by member-state facilities and co-funding), as well as a tangible instrument to create stronger ties between all types of knowledge-intensive industries and publicly-funded knowledge institutions. The institutionalisation of collaborations between industry and RIs (and the wider academic research communities) will help slash costs and allow industry to carry out the necessary (fundamental research) and shorten the time taken to create the innovations that Society and the world need.

The implementation of the ATTRACT Programme is seen by the current Consortium as part of the next EU Research Framework Programme (i.e. FP9). The Consortium considers that once the ATTRACT Phase-1 and ATTRACT Phase-2 Projects have proven themselves as breakthrough innovation generators to industrial and private investment communities across the world, a new, lasting, innovation eco-system will evolve between RIs, academic centres, RO and industry (see Figure 19 below). Achieving this will see a gradual reduction in demand for public funding to perpetuate the cycle.

Figure 14: Illustration of the natural synergy between the ATTRACT Phase-1 and ATTRACT Phase-2 Projects, whereby the end-point of Phase-1 (identifying breakthrough technologies and absorbing investment risk) is the starting point for of Phase-2 (reducing investment-risk by public support to up-scale radical technologies on the path to breakthrough innovation, so that market forces can then take over). The model – called ATTRACT Programme – can be expanded to cover more projects in a given science domain, but it can also be extended to cover other key-enabling technologies in various science domains that may subsequently start to create their own synergies.

THE ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT GOVERNANCE MODEL AND DECISION-MAKING PROCEDURES

The governance model has been set up to dovetail with the project's purpose as a seed-funding mechanism. It comprises a single layer, which is the Project Consortium Board (PCB). The PCB establishes two independent ad-hoc bodies:

- 1 | The Independent RDI Committee (IC).
- 2 | The Project Advisory Committee (PAC), whose internal composition is explained below.

The operational procedures for the PCB, including decision-making, conflict resolution and its relationship to the IC and the PAC, are described in the CA. The operational procedures for the IC and the PAC will be defined by themselves in order to ensure full independence.

The **PCB** manages the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project and is the ultimate decision-making body of the Phase-1 Project Consortium. Each Consortium partner will appoint one representative to the PCB. The PCB's principle tasks are to:

- > Steer the overall project.
- > Confirm the composition of the IC members as selected by the IC Chair for the purpose of peer-reviewed evaluations in the specific domains that the proposals address; the PCB will not confirm if it has proven concerns as to the integrity or independence of an IC member or as regards the competence in relation to the technologies set out in the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call.
- > Make changes to the Consortium Plan if necessary.

- > Approve the list of projects for funding, as established by the IC.
- > Appoint the PAC Chair and appoint the other PAC members.
- > Confirm the replacement of PAC members in the event of non-performance or conflict of interest.

PCB meetings will be held at least twice a year. At its first meeting after the start of the Project (Effective Date), the PCB elects a chairperson from among its members. The first meeting of the PCB shall be chaired by the PCB Member appointed by the Co-ordinator. The Chair will invite the other PCB members to a meeting and will also prepare the meeting's agenda.

PCB decision-making: The best way of reaching agreement within the PCB is through consensus. In principle, a PCB meeting decision is only valid if all nine partner organisations have attended the meeting (quorum) and the Minutes of the meeting have been approved. If the quorum is not reached, the PCB Chair will set a new meeting date within 15 days. If the quorum is still not reached, then decisions can be taken by a two-thirds majority vote without the full quorum being reached. Each Phase-1 Project Consortium partner organisation has one vote. PCB decisions may also be taken without a physical PCB meeting, provided the Chair has circulated a written document to all Phase-1 Project Consortium partners and full consensus is achieved. The Project Co-ordinator will advise the PCB Chair and organise the logistics of the PCB meetings (including taking the Minutes). The detailed operational procedures of the PCB are described in the CA.

The following representatives from the Phase-1 Project Consortium partner organisations will be members of the PCB:

Table 3: Overview of ATTRACT Phase-1 Project PCB members

NAME	ORGANISATION	POSITION
Thierry Lagrange	1/ CERN	Head of Industry, Procurement and Knowledge Transfer.
Luke Collins	2 /EIRMA	EIRMA Rapporteur.
Andrew McCarthy	3/ EMBL	Team Leader (Synchrotron Crystallography) at the EMBL-Grenoble.
Michael Krisch	4/ ESRF	Head of Division – Instrumentation Services & Development Division.
Kalevi Ekman	5/ AALTO	Professor of integrated product development and machine design at AALTO University & Director of AALTO University Design Factory.
Paolo Mutti	6/ ILL	Head of Instrument Control Division.
Jonathan Wareham	7/ ESADE	Dean (Faculty & Research) of Business & Law Schools.
Thomas Tschentscher	8/ XFEL	Scientific Director.
Mark Casali	9/ ESO	Head of Technology Development.

The **IC** is the ad-hoc external body for (Table 6):

- > The preparation of the contents for the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call.
- > The evaluation of the received project proposals.
- > The ranking for funding for the ATTRACT Phase-1 Consortium.

It is a fully independent committee of top-level experts in the domain of Detector & Imaging technology from science, industry and the private investor community. The Chair of the IC will remain the same throughout to ensure continuity and consistency. The PCB has appointed the IC Chair: Professor Sergio Bertolucci of the University of Bologna. All IC Members will sign a letter of appointment, including the mandate for their tasks and provisions on the prevention of conflicts of interest of the IC Members arising from economic interests, or political or national affinity.

The IC will not have representatives of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Consortium organisations (nor of any legally affiliated entity) to avoid any bias toward Call Themes, specific applicant consortia or individual evaluations. The IC has the following responsibilities:

- > Establish RDI topics for the Open Call, based on the already described bottom-up approach with different Detection & Imaging technology communities across Europe in accordance with the project's objectives as set out in the Grant Agreement.
- > Evaluate and rank submitted ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call proposals, recommend their selection to the PCB for funding by the ATTRACT Phase-1 Consortium.
- > Contribute to the follow-up of funded projects (in close collaboration with other WPs) to ensure excellence throughout these projects' duration.

Ranking of evaluated proposals will be achieved through consensus, save where in exceptional cases agreement cannot be reached. If there is a tie (for example on the bottom two proposals eligible for funding), then the IC-Chair has the deciding vote.

The Co-ordinator is the intermediary between the ATTRACT Phase-1 Consortium and the EC as the Funding Authority for the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project.

The Project Coordinator (PC) for the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project is Markus Nordberg.

As the former Resources Co-ordinator of the ATLAS Experiment at CERN (2001-2013), Nordberg has wide experience of implementing (very) large international collaborations and managing complex financial programmes with many stakeholders. Furthermore, Nordberg has been responsible for the initiation of several CERN-led EU-funded projects in FP7 and H2020, has co-created IdeaSquare innovation centre at CERN, and is a regular speaker on the future of Europe's Research Infrastructures at EC events in Brussels. Nordberg will be assisted by Pablo Garcia Tello, head of the section of EU (European Union) strategic initiatives at CERN. Tello has extensive experience in co-ordinating EC projects such as COOPERATEUS, SUNJET, NEARS and AERA-PRO among others. In the past, he has also contributed to the creation of the EC Public Private Partnership SPIRE. The responsibilities of the Coordinator are:

1 | Toward the Consortium partners:

- > Monitoring the Consortium partners' compliance with their obligations.
- > Transmitting documents and information connected with the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project to all Consortium partners.
- > Collecting and reviewing financial and technical progress data for the submission of periodic reports to evidence project deliverables and provide specific requested documents to the EC.
- > Administering the financial contribution of the EC to the Consortium partners and fulfilling the project's financial, legal and project management tasks vis-à-vis the EC.

2 | Toward the day-to-day operation of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project as a seed-funding mechanism:

- > Managing the PAO.
- > Concluding TPPA with successful ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call applicants on behalf of the Consortium partners³².
- > Distributing the funding to ATTRACT Open Call applicants (as 'Third-Parties').
- > Acting as the legal point of contact for the projects funded by the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project.

³² In case the Co-ordinator (i.c. CERN) is selected for a Third-Party contract, a different ATTRACT Phase-1 Project Consortium partner will sign the TPPA on behalf of the other Consortium members.

The **PAO** is the dedicated administrative body for the delivery of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project. It is physically located at the offices of the Co-ordinator. The PAO will:

- > Manage all technical and administrative processes related to the publication of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call and the electronic submission of proposals (Including acting as helpdesk for applicants).
- > Assist the IC during the evaluation process and notify applicants of the evaluation outcomes (following ranking approval by the PCB).
- > Develop the TPPA template and negotiate and prepare templates for signature between the PC and the successful ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call applicants (e.g. the 'Third-Parties').
- > Organise the financial distribution of the allocated funds to the successful ATTRACT Phase-1 Open Call applicants (e.g. 'Third-Parties').
- > Support the individual WPs in the delivery of their tasks in building networks, communicating and disseminating information about the funded projects and the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project approach and the analysis of impact.
- > Provide administrative and logistic assistance to the PCB, PAC and IC upon their request, including the organisation of Consortium and PAC meetings, preparation of minutes and of IC evaluation sessions.
- > Prepare all required financial and technical progress reports to the EC, except for those reports that are assigned to the WP participants under the WPs as deliverables.
- > Assist the Co-ordinator in his/her role as the point of contact for the EC.
- > Assistance to the Consortium partners in their obligations with respect to communication and exploitation of the Project deliverables under the Grant Agreement. This includes co-ordination of communication between the TTOs and the Communication Departments of the Consortium ERI.
- > Assistance to the Consortium in the organisation of events, including workshops and conferences.

The PAO is staffed by experts employed by the co-ordinating organisation and has a proven track record in managing large international research projects (Table 4):

Table 4: Overview of ATTRACT Phase-1 Project PAO members

NAME	ORGANISATION	POSITION
Markus Nordberg	1/ CERN	Co-ordinator. Head of Resources Development, Development and Innovation (IPT-DI).
Marzio Nessi	1/ CERN	Advisor. Leader of the Neutrino Platform.
Sandy Petitfrere	1/ CERN	Administrative Assistant.
Pablo Tello	1/ CERN	Co-ordinator. Section Head of the Development of EU Projects & Initiatives within the CERN EU Support Group.

The **PAC** consists of representatives of European public and private entities. The PCB has appointed Professor John Wood from the Association of Commonwealth Universities as the Chair of the PAC for the duration of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project. The Chair has already selected the other PAC members and these have been appointed by the PCB. The PAC Chair may invite external advisers as needed. For example: The PAC may invite Prof. Henry Chesbrough, who coined the term “Open Innovation” and Director of the Open Innovation Program at the University of California - Berkeley’s Haas Business School, for advice on the implementation of the Open Innovation principles in relation to the up-scaling of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project to the full-scale ATTRACT Programme.

All PAC Members will sign a letter of appointment before the Grant Agreement is concluded -. The tasks of the PAC are to provide strategic advice on a possible extension of the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project beyond its envisaged term. In providing such advice, the PAC may establish an open dialogue with public and private stakeholders, including high-level policy makers, to raise their interest in making follow-on investments to the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project.

The PAC will report on its progress to the PCB on a regular basis and as requested by the PCB. Table 5 presents an overview of the members of the PAC.

Table 5: Overview of members of the PAC

NAME	ORGANISATION & POSITION	RELEVANCE FOR ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT
John Wood	PAC Chair	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Former Secretary General of the Association of Commonwealth Universities (ACU), former Chair of the first ESFRI Roadmap; - Former Chair of European XFEL International Steering Committee; - Former Chief Executive of the Council of Central Laboratories (UK Research Council); - Chair of the Global Research Data Alliance; - Chair of the South African Research Infrastructure Roadmap Group.
Monica Beltrametti	Director, Naverlabs	Former Chief Services Research Officer, Xerox, Vice-President of the Xerox Innovation Group and Director of the Xerox Research Centre Europe (XRCE). She supported and created ventures that were later acquired by companies such as SAP and EMC.
Sergio Bertolucci	Chair of the IC; Professor, at the University of Bologna	Currently member of the Restricted Panel of the European Committee for Future Accelerators. Formerly also Vice-President and a member of the Board of the Italian National Institute of Nuclear Physics.
Francisco Javier Cáceres	Director General, INEUSTAR (Spanish Association for Scientific Industry)	International Senior Consultant in the field of innovation and advises on new processes, models and tools. He was also Director of R&D at IESA, a company based in San Sebastian, and has been Director General of the Basque Country Association of Electronic and Information Technologies.

NAME	ORGANISATION & POSITION	RELEVANCE FOR ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT
Leopold Demiddeleer	Strategic Advisor	<p>Dr. Léopold Demiddeleer, Ph.D., is the President of the Board at the European Industrial Research Management Association. Dr. Demiddeleer served as Senior Executive Vice-President of Future Businesses, Future Businesses Director and Co-Chairman of the New Business Board and the Corporate R&D at Solvay S.A. He joined Solvay in 1981. He has also served as the New Business Development Director at Solvay since 2001. From 1981 to 2001, he was responsible for several research and development initiatives in catalyst high performance materials, polyethylene, polymers and global polyolefins. He started his career in 1976 teaching Mathematics and Physics. He served as a Director of Corporate R&D and New Business Development at Solvay Specialty Polymers Italy S.p.A. He has been an Independent Director of McPhy Energy SA since May 22, 2015. Dr. Demiddeleer is a Member of Advisory Board at Conduit Ventures Limited. He served as a Director of Polytronics, Inc. He served as the Chairman of the Supervisory Board at McPhy Energy SA. He was a Member of Advisory Board at Pangaea Ventures Ltd. Dr. Demiddeleer holds a Ph.D. in Physical Chemistry from Brussels University.</p>
Candace Johnson	President, EBAN (European Business Angels Network)	<p>Co-founder of SES, the world's pre-eminent satellite group and the architect of SES Global. She is also the founding President of Europe Online Investments, the world's first internet-based online service and satellite broadband network, and the founder of Loral Cyberstar-Teleport Europe, Europe's first independent private trans-border satellite communications network. She is the founding President of VATM, the Association of Private Telecom Operators in Germany, and of the Global Telecom Women's Network.</p>
Gernot Spiegelberg	Senior Principal, Industrial Data Space, SIEMENS AG	<p>Since May 2008, Gernot Spiegelberg has headed as Vice President Siemens AG's Lighthouse Project eCar in the company's central research. Previously, in his role as Executive Vice President and CTO, Spiegelberg bore global responsibility for group Strategy / Technology at Siemens VDO Automotive AG. Spiegelberg holds a doctorate in engineering and an honorary professorship and teaching position at the Technical University of Budapest. He has held a variety of management positions in industry, including 18 years at Daimler-Chrysler where he was responsible for global advance development in mechatronics. Gernot Spiegelberg is selected as a Rudolf-Diesel-Industry Senior Fellow at the Technical University of Munich since July 2010. In Siemens his focus today are smart services in IoT with smart autonomous agents and Industrial Data Space IDS. Parallel he is busy at the University of Skt. Gallen for "disruptive business models" and shares several BoM gremia in automotive and automation domain.</p>

NAME	ORGANISATION & POSITION	RELEVANCE FOR ATTRACT PHASE-1 PROJECT
Daria Tataj	Strategy Advisor, Board Member and entrepreneur	Daria Tataj is a Strategy Advisor, Board Member and entrepreneur. She has over 20 years of business and public policy experience in emerging markets and in the most advanced global knowledge economies. Dr. Tataj is the Chairwoman of High-Level Advisors to Carlos Moedas, the EU Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation. She also advises the World Economic Forum, multinational companies, governments, investors and high-potential teams. The CEO of TATAJ Innovation, a strategy and investment firm, she founded the company with a mission to help cities build innovation districts.
Patrick Terroir	President of Innovation Legal, Chair of the LESI Patent and Technology Licensing Committee, Legal Advisor	Patrick graduated from Sciences Po, University of Paris II (doctorate in law) and the National School of High Administration. He occupied several positions in French public administration, in the Ministry of Economy and Finances and the Caisse des Dépôts. In 2006, he set up an innovation department in CDC, which operated in the patent economy, technology transfers from universities and SME support and created France Brevets. Since February 2014, Patrick Terroir, became a lawyer and created Innovation Legal, which is active in innovation and the intellectual property economy. He tendered advice for several European programmes and chairs the Patent and Technology Licensing Committee of Licensing Executive Society International since May 2015. Patrick Terroir is also a teacher in Innovation Economics at Sciences Po, Paris and wrote several articles and reports (among them: "Creating new infrastructure and a new mode of functioning for a true knowledge economy in Europe", Europartenaires Report, January 2013, "Rebalancing the Patent Economy", IAM review, March 2014, "The SMEs and the patent challenge", Special issue of Les Nouvelles (LESI), September 2017).

Table 6: IC Members

IC MEMBER	IC FUNCTION
Sergio Bertolucci	Chair
Cinzia da Via	Co-ordinator
Ricardo Graciani Diaz	Member
Michel Spiro	Member
Andrea Cuomo	Member
Matthias Kaiserswerth	Member
Ralf Kaiser	Member
Norbert Wermes	Member
Bernd Schmitt	Member
Pawel Sobkowicz	Member
Dimitra Darambara	Member
SiJbren Otto	Member

Figure 15 below summarises the ATTRACT Phase-1 Project governance structure:

Figure 15: ATTRACT Phase-1 Project governance structure.

THE ATTRACT PROGRAMME

EMBL

ESADE
Business School

Systematizing serendipity for big science infrastructures: the ATTRACT project

AUTHORS:

- Jonathan Wareham, Laia Pujol Priego and Angelo Romasanta (Esade)
- Markus Nordberg and Pablo Garcia Tello (CERN)
- Thomas Wareham Mathiassen (Technical University of Denmark-DTU)

≡ INDEX

1. Introduction

2. Background: big science and social impact

2.1 Definition and
history

2.2 Impact assessment
of big science

3. Serendipity

3.1 Definitions and
typologies of
serendipity

3.2 Realizing
serendipity

4. ATTRACT

4.1 Philosophy

4.2 Purpose, design
and results to date

4.3 The 170 funded
ATTRACT projects

4.4 Modes towards
serendipity

4.4.1 Combination
of different
technologies

4.4.2 Building on
previous research

4.4.3 Applying
technology to
another field

4.4.4 Using artificial
intelligence or
machine learning

5. Discussion

5.1 Implications for
theory

5.2 Implications for
policy and practice

6. Conclusions

7. Acknowledgments

8. References

Systematizing serendipity for big science infrastructures: the ATTRACT project

AUTHORS

Ramon Llull
University - Esade

- Jonathan Wareham
- Laia Pujol Priego
- Angelo Romasanta

CERN

- Markus Nordberg
- Pablo Garcia Tello

Technical University
of Denmark-DTU

- Thomas Wareham
- Mathiasen

ABSTRACT

This paper explores how policy can promote the application of scientific research beyond its original purview. We analyze ATTRACT¹, a novel policy instrument in the European Commission's Horizon 2020 program, aiming to harness the detection and imaging technologies of the leading European research infrastructures towards entrepreneurship. In this initiative, 170 projects were funded with €100,000 for each to develop a proof-of-concept commercial application within one year. Leveraging the unique dataset from the projects funded under ATTRACT, our study finds different serendipity modes compared to the previously proposed typologies, as follows: (1) building on previous research, (2) combining different technologies, (3) applying a technology into a different field, and (4) using artificial intelligence or machine learning. This study contributes to the emerging literature on serendipity by showing the potential of policy interventions to enable individuals and organizations to find unexpected commercial applications of big science research.

¹The members of ATTRACT are as follows: the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), European Southern Observatory (ESO), European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), European X-Ray Free Electron Laser Facility (European XFEL), the Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL), Aalto University, Esade Business School, and the European Industrial Research Management Association (EIRMA).

1. Introduction

Some of the most pervasive technologies in society today, such as the internet, medical diagnostics and treatments, and information and communication technologies, result from leveraging the research generated by big science infrastructures to areas beyond their direct scientific purview. While the potential of big science to create social, cultural, and economic impacts is acknowledged, uncertainty remains on how these big science infrastructures can deliberately find novel applications outside of their immediate scopes of research. Moreover, there are also questions regarding the extent to which **policymakers can play an active role in enabling these research centers to find novel uses for their research that were previously unanticipated**. Exploring these questions, this paper examines a novel policy response by the European Union to promote the commercialization of technologies from some of Europe's most impactful research infrastructures.

The term serendipity has been evoked to describe various unintended discoveries, typically with some beneficial outcomes. For example, Fleming's discovery of penicillin is often cited as a serendipitous discovery with tremendous social value. The definition of serendipity, however, can be ambiguous. The Merriam Webster dictionary defines serendipity as "the faculty or phenomenon of finding valuable or agreeable things not sought for" (Merriam-Webster, 2020), while the Oxford dictionary defines it as "the occurrence and development of events by chance in a happy or beneficial way" (Oxford University Press, 2019). **In the management and innovation literature, creating conditions that foster serendipity is considered desirable for managers and policy-makers** (Yaqub, 2018).

On the surface, the argument that serendipity can play a positive role in scientific processes and policy has its immediate value as ex-post, anecdotal narratives with limited normative value. However, this misconception comes from interpreting serendipity as mere happenstance instead of resulting from deliberate effort (de Rond, 2014). A systematic analysis of serendipity is useful because it offers a more nuanced understanding of its antecedents and mechanisms (e.g., Yaqub, 2018; Garud 2018). By identifying the formative conditions of serendipity, the design of mechanisms to realize the peripheral benefits of scientific research infrastructures

can be improved; in effect, one could attempt to systematize serendipity. However, to date, most of the research has been speculative or based on small-sample, anecdotal evidence from previous scientific discoveries.

Capturing the value of big science requires simulating exploration and the simultaneous fostering of commercial development through risk absorption and support

This study examines the ATTRACT project, a €20M-funded initiative within the Horizon 2020 Framework Program that aims to systematize the discovery of breakthrough applications of imaging and detection technologies from the leading European science research infrastructures. Recognizing that the full potential of these detection and imaging technologies is unknown, ATTRACT was formulated with the understanding that capturing the value of big science will require both stimulating exploration and the simultaneous fostering of commercial development through risk absorption and support. Accordingly, **ATTRACT supported 170 projects with seed-funding grants of €100,000 each to leverage their various technologies** towards sustainable businesses and greater economic returns for the European economy.

Analyzing how the large research infrastructures can find new impactful uses for their science is highly relevant. Given their extreme sophistication and required investment levels, research infrastructures are normally funded by taxpayers via national ministries or funding agencies – often in pan-national consortia. As such, **it bears upon policymakers to seek mechanisms to optimize the potential socioeconomic value of these public investments**. ATTRACT brings six of the largest European scientific research infrastructures, which are also members of the EIROforum, together; they are as follows: European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), European Southern Observatory (ESO), European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), European X-ray Free Electron Laser Facility (European XFEL), and the Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL). These organizations work in diverse domains, such as nuclear, particle, and condensed matter physics; life sciences; molecular biology; astronomy; materials science; structural biology; and chemistry.

The 170 projects funded under ATTRACT provide a unique dataset to examine the processes towards serendipity. In this analysis, we find the following modes: (1) building on previous research, (2) combining different technologies, (3) applying technology into a different field and (4) using artificial intelligence or machine learning. We validate the previous typologies of serendipity and extend these notions by describing new categories. Unlike the previous studies that examined serendipity ex-ante, this study explores purposeful actions carried out in the pursuit of serendipity. Moreover, we explore how the intentional nature of the policy intervention by ATTRACT can help in finding new, previously unexplored applications of research technologies.

Unlike the previous studies that examined serendipity ex-ante, this study explores purposeful actions carried out in the pursuit of serendipity

The study proceeds by reviewing the history of big science, the polemics of its underlying social value, and the mechanisms and measures that policymakers use to stimulate the application of science towards social and economic impacts. We describe the literature on serendipity, summarizing the extant literature and the main research questions. We present the ATTRACT project and explore how it attempts to systematize serendipity. Contributing to the serendipity literature, we summarize the 170 projects funded under the call and examine the various modes used to discover previously unanticipated applications. We conclude with observations concerning serendipity and describe trajectories for future initiatives concerning big science and socioeconomic value.

2. Background: big science and social impact

In the following, we explore the history of big science and the issues related to its impact on society.

2.1 Definition and history

Big science infrastructures are defined by Florio and Sirtori (2016) as institutions with a) high capital intensity, b) long-lasting facilities or networks, c) operating in monopoly or oligopoly conditions affected by externalities, d) who produce social benefits via the generation of new knowledge (either pure or applied). As argued by Giudice (2012), the evolution of big science began early in the twentieth century with examples such as the factory-like conditions where Heike Kamerlingh Onnes made seminal discoveries on superfluidity and superconductivity in the early 1900s, or the Wilson Observatory, completed in 1917 and made famous by Edwin Hubble. What began to characterize research as big science was how it differed from the ideal of the lone genius in the laboratory with simple table-top experiments.

The cyclotron provides an early example of how big science research can have alternative applications for socioeconomic impact

This **new model of scientific exploration was fully institutionalized by Ernest Orlando Lawrence at the University of California**, Berkeley with the development of the cyclotron, which is a device for accelerating nuclear particles to very high velocities to bombard, disintegrate and form completely new elements and radioactive isotopes. While the first cyclotron was merely a simple 4-inch device that could be held in the human hand, over time, larger versions that could achieve greater energy levels were created. With each subsequent generation of the cyclotron, a larger number of physicists, engineers, and chemists were needed for construction, operation, and maintenance. More importantly, he advanced a form of team-based, collaborative science that contrasted with the isolated model of 'smaller science'² (Hiltzik, 2016) and later matured into large research teams with hundreds of scientists and engineers. This new type of industrialized

science eventually propagated to other American and European universities and was facetiously called the 'Cyclotron Republic' by Lawrence's numerous admirers and rivals (Hiltzik, 2016).

The cyclotron also provides an early example of **how big science research can have alternative applications for socioeconomic impact**. A serendipitous by-product of Lawrence's lab was the production of radioactive isotopes useful for cancer treatment (Hiltzik, 2016). With the help of his brother John Lawrence, a medical doctor who became the director of the university's Medical Physics Laboratory, Ernest was able to recraft the cyclotron's narrative to court funders intrigued by the potential of important isotopes. In a Faustian spirit, the laboratory metaphorically produced oncology-focused isotopes by day, while discretely conducting basic research by night, and while many on the team bemoaned the fact that commitments to medical research hindered advancement in fundamental physics, this shrewd strategy enabled Lawrence to fund his constantly moving targets of higher energy levels that required more sophisticated hardware, complex operating organizations, and generated unprecedented costs. This tactic further **institutionalized the future relationship between big science and big funders**, be they philanthropies, national ministries of defense or energy, or increasingly, supranational-coalitions (Crease et al., 2016).

The rise of big science, however, is often associated with the Manhattan Project and the numerous technological innovations that were enhanced during WWII, such as radar and wireless communication. Motivated primarily by military and global political concerns, technological superiority was considered a central element of geopolitical competition (Galison and Hevly, 1992). This superiority was not limited to military research, although the defense industry was certainly a central protagonist. Espoused in the famous report of Vannevar Bush (1945), *Science: The Endless Frontier*,

²Quoting Luis Alvarez in Hiltzik (2015): There were no doors inside the Rad Lab. 'Its central focus was the cyclotron, on which everyone worked and which belonged to everyone equally (though perhaps more to Ernest). Everyone was free to borrow or use everyone else's equipment or, more commonly, to plan a joint experiment'. The team approach to physics, Alvarez judged, was 'Lawrence's greatest invention'. (Hiltzik 2015:129-30).

basic research was not only good for fundamental science but generated applied engineering and technologies that translated into products, spin-offs, jobs, and overall economic prosperity that benefited all social classes. The 'Bush legacy' (Wilson, 1991) was further catalyzed by the successful leap-start of the Soviet space program, an event that galvanized the American public to approve the astronomical funding levels of the American space program while having little concern for its scientific merit. With the perceived technological gap between the USA and the USSR, the Soviet space program was considered a severe existential threat that, similar to the Manhattan Project, could only be remedied by massive investments in basic, applied, and ever-bigger science (Giudice, 2012).

Currently, with the cold war decades in the past, the role of big science in society has transformed

Currently, with the cold war decades in the past, **the role of big science in society has transformed**. The perception of grand existential geopolitical threats has turned into a more disperse narrative. As a result, investments in big science motivated by national security or geopolitical stability have decreased. This decrease has weakened the sacrosanct link between nuclear physics, weapons research, and geopolitical security and, as a consequence, has reduced the primacy of fundamental physics (Galison and Hevly, 1992; Hiltzik, 2016). Moreover, the tenacious success of the Standard Model has left aspiring physicists scrambling for new avenues to conduct physics, leading them to astrophysics and cosmology, as well as more distant fields, such as biology and life sciences (Galison, 2016).

In addition, **the nature of big science infrastructures has become more heterogeneous**. Today, traditional particle accelerators and nuclear reactors work alongside synchrotron radiation, neutron scattering, and free electron laser facilities, where the empirical scope has widened to materials science, chemistry, energy, condensed matter physics, nanoscience, biology, biotechnology and pharmacology (Doing, 2018; Heinze and Hallonsten, 2017). Finally, big science infrastructures are no longer constrained by national security mandates. These infrastructures must now compete in a global scientific market with increased mobility, transparency, and competition. As such, they are often in positions where they need to justify their utility and efficiency across diverse scientific communities and policymakers (Hallonsten, 2014; Heidler and Hallonsten, 2015).

2.2 Impact assessment of big science

The previously described changes have transformed the political context in which big science operates. An important early figure looking into the **new challenges faced by big science** was Alvin Weinberg, director for the Oak Ridge National Laboratory, where uranium was enriched for the atomic bomb in its early years. In his important articles in *Science* (1961) and *Minerva* (1964 and 1963), he voiced his concerns that big science had become a bloated self-serving institution of bureaucracy and complacency, disconnected from more basic human and social needs (Crease *et al.*, 2016). At the same time, the softening of geopolitical ethos did not free big science from excessive political influence (Hellström and Jacob, 2012; Weinberg, 1964, 1963, 1961). In contrast, since public budgets require substantial political support, there were concerns **that champions may be tempted to sell and defend their visions with a certain level of sensationalism** (Scudellari, 2017). Moreover, there were worries that the business of blockbuster science could undermine the more serious and less sensational work of normal science (Hellström and Jacob, 2012). Weinberg then wanted to establish some criteria for which investments in big science could be evaluated against alternative social priorities (Hellström and Jacob, 2012).

An obvious point of departure is to evaluate the scientific productivity levels of big science infrastructures, which are typically evidenced through citation and patent counts. While quantitative evaluation of these measures is easy, they are also considered very imperfect proxies of scientific value, as well as poor indicators of the many peripheral benefits of big science infrastructures (OECD, 2003; Schopper, 2016). As an example, Bianco *et al.* (2017) argue that the International Space Station, which has cost over \$100 billion to build and \$2 billion a year to operate, has, as of 2017, only produced 34 refereed articles and 4 patents. Given their long cycle times, publication and patent counts favor more mature infrastructures and are often used as post hoc justifications of sunk-cost investments.

The normal focus for researchers attempting to evaluate the value of big scientific research infrastructures is on the impacts of direct spending on high-tech procurement with subsequent multiplier effects

Broadening the scope beyond scientific impact, the normal focus for researchers attempting to evaluate the value of

big scientific research infrastructures is on the impacts of direct spending on high-tech procurement with subsequent multiplier effects (Autio *et al.*, 2003; Castelnovo *et al.*, 2018). For instance, aggregating numerous studies of CERN, Schopper (2016) estimates that **for every euro spent on high-tech products, an additional 4.2 euros are generated in supporting industries**. Beyond the impacts on immediate suppliers, another narrative used to justify investments in scientific research infrastructures are technology spinoffs, with their corresponding or assumed economic growth, job creation, and tax revenue (Aschhoff and Sofka, 2009). Here, NASA may be the most prolific example, boasting over 2,000 spinoffs since 19764 (NASA Spinoff)³. Like the early cyclotrons at Berkeley, **the value of spinoffs is that they often commercialize technologies in applications outside of a laboratory's principal scientific purview**, demonstrating how major research infrastructures can generate impacts beneficial to society without detriment to its main mission (OECD, 2014).

The value of spinoffs is that they often commercialize technologies in applications outside of a laboratory's principal scientific purview, demonstrating how major research infrastructures can generate impacts beneficial to society

An important characteristic of technology spinoffs as a metric of social value is that the benefits are assumed to accrue to society well beyond the immediate scientific community, and this assumption is important in justifying the investments to taxpayers. However, estimating the indirect, or even direct, economic impacts becomes even more problematic when the technological derivatives are not protected by patents, trademarks, or citations (Schopper, 2016), as is often the case. Given that the political mandate of many research infrastructures is to generate scientific knowledge towards greater social value (Hammett, 1941), the decision not to protect technologies with property rights is frequent and explicit.

These practices are consistent with the ethos of open science and open innovation movements (Chesbrough, 2003; European Commission, 2016), **as well as specific mandates from funding agencies to make publicly funded research data accessible**, with research results published in open access platforms and FAIR data principles (European Commission, 2012). The most famous and recent case

was the World Wide Web (specifically, HTTP, URL, HTML), i.e., when Tim Berners-Lee convinced CERN's managers in 1993 to place it in the public domain and make the IP freely available to everyone. By accepting this case, CERN effectively agreed not to draw revenues or economic value from it. In the words of a CERN senior scientific officer: 'In the case of a conflict between revenue generation and dissemination, dissemination takes precedence' (World Intellectual Property Organization, 2010). For a technology with this level of impact, any quantification of its socio-economic value almost approaches the surreal.

Researchers have attempted to derive more holistic models by conceptually defining the alternative social benefits of research infrastructures (Autio *et al.*, 1996). For example, Florio *et al.* (2016) derive a model that is based on the following six main dimensions:

- 1) impact on firms due to technological spillovers produced by access to new knowledge and learning by doing;
- 2) benefits to employees and students through increases in human capital;
- 3) the social value of scientific publications for scientists;
- 4) cultural benefits through outreach activities;
- 5) additional services provided to consumers; and
- 6) the value of the scientific discovery.

An earlier, complementary perspective was offered by Autio *et al.* (2004) who derived a number of propositions related to **the positive value that a big science infrastructure can have on its ecosystem of suppliers**. These include pushing the frontiers of technology and engineering standards, reducing uncertainty surrounding standards and technology investments, sharing their capacity to manage highly complex projects, aggregating highly diverse and specialized knowledge domains towards radical learning and novel combinations, access to international networks, prestige and reputation, network formation, an exceptional scale and a scope that supports extreme prototyping and testing.

Overall, the indicators are not perfect in terms of assessing the impacts of research infrastructures since they can be insufficient proxies of what they are measuring (e.g., citations), suffer from time-lag effects (Schopper, 2016), and can be myopic in capturing the value provided (spillover effects, human capital formation, or cultural value). As argued in Boisot *et al.* (2011), **the more that a research infrastructure deals**

³<https://spinoff.nasa.gov/database/>

with fundamental research, the greater the uncertainty surrounding the future value of the outputs. The lack of reliable data, or well-understood causality, means that more holistic conceptualizations are excessively difficult to quantify and can lead to politically oriented narratives.

In summary, the previous discussion leads to the following conclusions:

- For research at the forefront of science, a variety of big science organizations have been created with facilities, infrastructures, and instrumentation with unprecedented technical sophistication.
- With questions on how limited public resources are allocated, concerns have arisen on the social and economic value of big science and how to effectively measure these impacts.

- Despite these worries, big science infrastructures have a consistent track record in terms of finding alternative applications for their technologies that have tangible impacts on society.
- While it is common for big science to find serendipitous value in areas previously unanticipated, there is a limited amount of rigorous empirical research on the nature of serendipity and how it can be proactively cultivated.

We, therefore, review the literature on serendipity and its mechanisms in the following section.

3. Serendipity

Serendipity refers to a broad, multifaceted phenomenon related to the unanticipated discovery of something beneficial. As it has been used in various contexts, we trace its various conceptualizations over time. Moreover, we describe the current understanding of how serendipity can be fostered.

3.1 Definitions and typologies of serendipity

The term serendipity was coined by writer Horace Walpole in 1754, who was inspired by the Persian fairy tale, *Three Princes of Serendip* (Cunha *et al.*, 2010; Rosenman, 2001). He refers to serendipity as an unexpected discovery found from the combination of accident and sagacity (Rosenman, 2001). Sagacity refers to having perception and sound judgment, or in other words, a prepared mind. As such, instead of being merely interchangeable with the words luck, happenstance or providence, **serendipity is better seen as a capability requiring the focus of attention** (de Rond, 2014). An equivalent formulation can be seen in the context of entrepreneurial opportunity, where serendipity has been seen as the combination of directed search, favorable accidents and prior knowledge (Dew, 2009). By stripping away the random and sometimes mystical aspects of serendipity, it becomes a concept that can be subject to rigorous evaluation, allowing an examination of its triggers, antecedents and mechanisms.

By stripping away the random and sometimes mystical aspects of serendipity, it becomes a concept that can be subject to rigorous evaluation, allowing an examination of its triggers, antecedents and mechanisms

A methodical attempt to understand serendipity was initiated by Robert Merton in the 1950s, which eventually resulted in a book dedicated to serendipity in 2004 (Merton and Barber, 2004). Yaqub (2018) conducted a systematic review of Merton's archives to identify four specific archetypes of serendipity. Mainly focusing on scientific discoveries, he organizes these according to a) whether there is a targeted line of inquiry; and b) the type of solution discovered.

Yaqub (2018) defines **Walpolian serendipity** as a targeted line of inquiry that leads to discoveries that researchers were not in search of (solution to a different problem). **Mertonian**

serendipity happens where the desired solution is achieved via an unexpected route (targeted problem – different path). **Bushian serendipity** is where untargeted exploratory research leads to a solution for a well-known problem. Finally, **Stephanian serendipity** is where untargeted research finds an unsought solution that may find a future application.

However, even earlier than Yaqub (2018), de Rond (2014) describes a different framework for the structure of serendipity. While he also organizes serendipity in a 2x2 matrix, he divides it differently according to a) whether the solution was the intended target and b) whether the original research design was causal to the solution. In his work, de Rond evokes the term *pseudo-serendipity* to describe when the solutions are intended in the first place, compared to (only) serendipity, where the solutions are completely unanticipated.

One key difference between the two is that de Rond (2014) already assumes that there is an intended target for serendipity to occur, while Yaqub (2018) also permits untargeted search in his framework. Nonetheless, we can see some equivalence between their categories. For instance, while not exactly the same, pseudo-serendipity corresponds to the Mertonian formulation of serendipity, while de Rond's serendipity is equivalent to the Walpolian formulation. Another difference is that whether the discovered solution is a consequence of random variation or deliberate design is not adequately captured by Yaqub's recent typology.

The role of design in serendipity is further emphasized in the work of Garud *et al* (2018). Taking insights from the evolutionary biology literature, they introduce the term 'exaptation' to the innovation literature to refer to the "emergence of functionalities for scientific discoveries that were unanticipated ex-ante." They identify two forms of exaptation, as follows: *franklins and miltons*.

— *Franklins* refer to the supplementary usage of existing structures in areas in which they were not originally intended for use (e.g., using coins as screwdrivers).

— *Miltons* refer to discoveries without a currently known function. A widely known image to illustrate miltons is that of spandrels, i.e., the triangular space unintentionally created by the shape of arches, which were later used as a blank canvas for painting (Bahar, 2018).

In contrast to the previous formulations of serendipity, Fink *et al.* (2017) propose another perspective altogether, which is based on the crossovers of interdependent components. In an experimental study, they show that components early on do not have much benefit, as their utility depends on the existence of other components. However, as the innovation process continues and other components appear, **the potential of this original set of components can suddenly manifest**. This moment, which seems to come out of nowhere, is what is perceived as serendipity. Accordingly, they explain that serendipity is not only a matter of happenstance but is a result of the components' delayed fruition, which occurs from the existence of other important components.

Serendipity is not only a matter of happenstance but is a result of the components' delayed fruition, which occurs from the existence of other important components

Finally, it is also important to note another field where the term serendipity has also gained ground, as it gives insights into what differentiates serendipity from other similar concepts. In the field of information systems, serendipity has become an important metric in recommender systems (Kotkov *et al.*, 2016). Recommender systems seek to predict what rating a user would give to a certain product so that new products can be recommended. These systems have been the backbones powering widely used services such as Netflix, Spotify, and YouTube. In such systems, **serendipity means that users do not only receive results that are relevant but results that are significantly different from the user's previously rated items**. This component of surprise is what seems to define serendipity in this context.

3.2 Realizing serendipity

Aside from attempting to find better definitions of serendipity and understanding its nature, there has also been much progress made on the **various factors or mechanisms that can lead to serendipity**. McCay-Peet and Toms (2015)

propose a process model for how individuals discover and perceive serendipitous events. Their model consists of the following components:

- Trigger
- Connection
- Follow-up
- Valuable outcome

The trigger refers to environmental cues sparking the interest of the individual. This trigger is then connected by the individual to their previous knowledge and experiences. Individuals then follow-up on these triggers to obtain a valuable outcome. The surprise occurs from noticing the unexpected thread present from the previous processes.

The strategies that individuals can pursue to increase the likelihood of serendipity include varying their routines, being observant, making mental space, relaxing their boundaries, drawing on previous experiences, looking for patterns and seizing opportunities

The conditions that promote serendipity have also been explored. For instance, the strategies that individuals can pursue to increase the likelihood of serendipity include "varying their routines, being observant, making mental space, relaxing their boundaries, drawing on previous experiences, looking for patterns and seizing opportunities" (Makri *et al.*, 2014). Yaqub (2018) also describes four mechanisms that we summarize as (1) examining deviations from theory, (2) activating previously acquired knowledge and experiences from individuals, (3) tolerating errors and following up on such occurrences, and (4) leveraging networks. In the organizational context, Cunha *et al.* (2010) identify some conditions related to serendipity, including boundary spanning, mindfulness, social networks, teamwork, free space for creativity and opportunities for playing with ideas.

Artificial intelligence has also been used to find novel solutions to various challenges. Computational methods can aid in the search for interesting information, enabling the discovery of new knowledge domains that have been previously unexplored (Arvo, 1999; Beale, 2007). In drug discovery, for instance, it has been used to repurpose drugs to new therapeutic areas (Mak and Pichika, 2019). As progress in the field increases, artificial systems that "catalyze, evaluate

and leverage serendipitous occurrences themselves" are also increasingly explored (Corneli *et al.*, 2014).

While serendipity at the personal and organizational level has been emerging, the literature on how serendipity can be actively pursued at a macro-level is still limited. Garud *et al.* (2018) describe arrangements to induce exaptation of science, as follows: exaptive pools, exaptive events, and exaptive forums. Exaptive pools refer to the maintenance of scientific discoveries such as through patent and publication databases. These ideas, however, remain decoupled until they are activated by exaptive events, such as technology fairs and workshops. These possibilities can be further developed and contextualized through exaptive forums, where actors become increasingly entangled.

In summary, the extant literature on serendipity has mostly been speculative or based upon small-sample, anecdotal examples of scientific discoveries. Moreover, the previous studies mainly focus on the individual scientists, lacking understanding of **how serendipity can be induced at a more macro-level**. As such, questions remain on how serendipity can be cultivated towards finding market applications for science and how it can be cultivated, for instance, with the help of policy. To move the serendipity literature forward, there is a need for studies based on empirical evidence, preferably using quasi-experimental conditions. By examining the novel policy response ATTRACT, this study puts forward a rigorous empirical examination of serendipity.

4. ATTRACT

The ATTRACT project is a €20M-funded initiative within the Horizon 2020 Framework Program that aims to systematize the discovery of breakthrough applications of research from the leading European big science infrastructures. In the following section, we describe its underlying philosophy, aims and results to date.

4.1 Philosophy

The assertion that the products of scientific research centers can have value outside of their intended scientific purview is not new⁴. It was demonstrated clearly by Lawrence's early cyclotrons in oncology, and the idea was perhaps best institutionalized as an important policy driver by Bush, who advocated large investments in untargeted scientific research as a source of serendipitous discoveries or solutions (Bush, 1945; Yaqub, 2018). In a more liberal interpretation, the Bush legacy favors large investments in research for its unknowable scientific value, as well as numerous unknown benefits that accrue as socio-economic derivatives (education, spin-offs, job creation, etc.).

During the last three decades, policymakers have increasingly emphasized policies to accelerate innovation and economic growth (Edler and Fagerberg, 2017). Three main types of approaches have been developed.

1. The *mission-oriented approach* aims to support solutions to challenges that are part of an explicit political agenda. Here, policy-makers tend to anchor innovation policies in grand societal challenges, such as national defense, climate change, or other sustainable development goals (Galison, 2016; Galison and Hevly, 1992; Mazzucato, 2016; Mazzucato and Semieniuk, 2017; Mowery, 2012).
2. *Invention-oriented* approaches aim to stimulate the supply of inventions as derivatives of scientific discovery while leaving any commercial exploitation to the market (Bush, 1945; Wilson, 1991). This was the most widely adopted approach championed post-war by Bush, as policy-makers sought to advance science and technology as broad drivers of geopolitical policy (Galison, 2016; Galison and Hevly, 1992).
3. Finally, recent decades have seen *system-oriented* approaches that seek to foster interactions among the different actors taking part in the innovation ecosystem (Borrás and Laatsit, 2019; Lundvall, 2010; Lundvall and Borrás, 2009).

Within these main orientations, a wide range of policy instruments have been deployed in Europe to stimulate innovation (European Commission 2016), and different typologies have been suggested to understand them (e.g., Borrás and Edquist, 2013; Edler and Georghiou, 2007). The most widely accepted view considers instruments such as those focusing either on technology push or market pull. Technology push (supply-side) policies stimulate framework conditions and opportunities for innovation to thrive, including measures to support R&D collaboration, network formation, and incentives to attract highly skilled labor to focal regions and sectors. For example, in Europe, the Future and Emerging Technologies (FET) program has allocated €2.7 billion to pursue breakthrough ideas through unexplored collaborations of multidisciplinary scientific and cutting-edge engineering teams, which is indicative of the invention-oriented approach mentioned earlier.

Technology push policies stimulate framework conditions and opportunities for innovation to thrive, including measures to support R&D collaboration, network formation, and incentives to attract highly skilled labor to focal regions and sectors

Market pull (demand-side) interventions have been emphasized with greater frequency in the most recent literature (Edler and Georghiou, 2007; European Commission, 2016b; Rolfstam, 2009). This perception recognizes that the derivatives of basic scientific research have limited value if specific market-pull mechanisms are not in place to facilitate their entry to the market (Scherer, 1982; Schmookler, 1962).

Demand-side policy instruments include measures to foster investments by private capital (brokering, tech-transfer, IP, subsidies, etc.) or, alternatively, pre-commercial procurement to nurture financial liquidity, investment, and operational scale in start-ups and SMEs (Edler and Fagerberg, 2017; Rolfstam,

⁴Detailed information can be found at <https://attract-eu.com>

2009). However, instruments that simultaneously stimulate both the supply-side and demand-side dynamics, especially for early-stage, high-risk technologies, are less common (Cunningham *et al.*, 2013; European Commission, 2016b).

The challenge of bridging the supply and demand sides of the innovation cycle is not an exclusive concern of innovation policies. It is also a well-known challenge in entrepreneurship research, where it is frequently metaphorized as the valley of death

The challenge of bridging the supply and demand sides of the innovation cycle is not an exclusive concern of innovation policies. It is also a well-known challenge in entrepreneurship research, where it is frequently metaphorized as the valley of death (VoD) (Beard *et al.*, 2009; Hudson and Khazragui, 2013). This metaphor describes the difficult phase in product development and commercialization where **many viable products or start-ups do not survive for a variety of reasons.** Typically, these include excessive and unforeseen costs for research, prototyping, testing and manufacturing, limited product development budgets, ineffective coordination and expertise, sub-critical market exposure, and the inability to obtain sufficient internal or external funding to bring the product or start-up to a revenue-generating state (Frank *et al.*, 1996).

A substantial amount of research has focused on the various mechanisms that can be marshaled towards mitigating the VoD phenomenon, which include the following: innovation intermediaries (Islam, 2017); scientific parks; technology clusters and living labs (Almirall and Wareham, 2011); industry associations (Markham *et al.*, 2010); business incubators and accelerators; technology brokers and tech-transfer functions (Beard *et al.*, 2009); regional, national, and pan-national funding instruments, such as Horizon 2020, EIT and ERC of Europe, and NIH, NSF of the US (Hudson and Khazragui, 2013).

For technologies with high technology readiness levels, the VoD is potentially less fatal, particularly for incremental innovations with probable market uptake

Finally, particularly in the medical and life sciences fields, there has been a growth in initiatives in translational research (Butler, 2008). No single VoD scenario is applicable to all

technologies. For technologies with high technology readiness levels (TRL) (Banke, 2010), the VoD is potentially less fatal, particularly for incremental innovations with probable market uptake. This condition is typically addressed by risk mitigation functions performed by private investment and venture capital. However, technologies with low TRLs require more extensive interventions, typically with both risk absorption (seed funding and early industry involvement) and risk mitigation (public/private investment mechanisms). It is important to note that TRLs are highly context dependent; i.e., the technology may be very mature and tested in its original application at the scientific research installation (high TRL), but immature in a larger system of commercialization when used in a different sector or market (low TRL) (Héder, 2017).

4.2 Purpose, design and results to date

Imaging and detection technologies will have core functions in almost all technically sophisticated commercial products and will constitute an annual market of over \$100 billion in their own right

The main aim of ATTRACT is to harness and direct exploration towards breakthrough innovation opportunities in detection and imaging technologies, while also offering space for serendipity to stumble onto unforeseen applications. As such, there are no 'intended' technological applications or desired outcomes. Rather, the ATTRACT governance is designed to generate as many options and variety in the applications as possible. That acknowledged, **there are some obvious areas where detection and imaging technologies can be employed towards substantial, if not paradigmatic, advances in other domains.** Frost and Sullivan argue that imaging and detection technologies will have core functions in almost all technically sophisticated commercial products and will constitute an annual market of over \$100 billion in their own right (Frost & Sullivan, 2015). These domains include medical device and imaging technology, biotechnology, energy, advanced manufacturing, automation, microelectronics, materials and coatings, environment and sustainability, and information and communication technology.

On many dimensions, ATTRACT has been designed to directly address the ineffectual transition – or disconnection

– between the technology-push instruments (applied in the early phases) and the market-pull instruments (the later entry of private capital) (Auerswald and Branscomb, 2003; Wolfe et al., 2014). In this respect, **ATTRACT is distinctive from recent instruments, such as FET, given that the focal actors include both research infrastructures and industrial players, and equal protagonism is given to both the supply and demand sides.** This is enabled by the pre-existing relationships between research infrastructures and their industrial suppliers; that is, the highly specialized SMEs that have contributed to the engineering, construction, and operation of some of the world’s most sophisticated technologies. Thus, the industrial relevance and operational feasibility of the projects are verified from the start.

Specifically, for projects involving European research facilities and industrial organizations, the most immediate use of their technologies is guaranteed. In this sense, a first ‘internal market’ is assured. This ‘internal market’ paves the way for industry to target other applications and new commercial opportunities (i.e., the feasibility of the pilot technologies has been prototyped and tested in the real and demanding working conditions of big science facilities).

The completion of ATTRACT phase I is expected to lead to insights and findings that inform modifications and extensions to the design of ATTRACT phase II and related innovation policy initiatives. **ATTRACT phase II will aim to take a select group of 10-20 validated projects from ATTRACT phase I and scale them towards technology readiness levels 5-8.** ATTRACT phase II is specifically designed to address the intermediate or secondary phases of the valley of death phenomenon, which requires greater scalability, maturity, and support. In addition, emphasis will be placed on the

transition to public sources of equity-based capital (e.g., the European Investment Fund and the European Investment Bank), as well as private capital sources, such as early and late-stage venture capital and private equity.

Table 1 highlights the main attributes of ATTRACT and how they are positioned relative to traditional EU funding instruments and private capital investments.

As of the writing of this paper, ATTRACT has implemented the following steps:

- 1. An open call was launched to solicit project proposals** (1,211 submitted) for leveraging detection and imaging technologies towards potentially commercially sustainable products or services. While not exclusive, the emphasis was on concepts at technology readiness levels 2-4. The call solicited proposals leveraging the following four main technology groups: a) sensors; b) data acquisition systems and computing; c) software and integration; and d) front- and back-end electronics.
- 2. All submissions were assessed on technical merit and innovation-potential.** Specifically, the evaluation dimensions included the project definition, scope, and technological feasibility, state-of-the-art, scientific/engineering merit, industrial potential, commercial feasibility, and social value.
- 3. 170 projects were awarded €100,000 for the development of a proof-of-concept or prototype** with an application outside of the original purview of the technology, over a period of one year.

Table 1. Comparison between ATTRACT and other funding instruments

	ATTRACT	EU range public funding instruments ¹	Private instrument
Approach for crossing the valley of death	Considers that breakthrough technologies need two steps of risk absorption and risk mitigation.	Assumes that only one step is needed – normally risk mitigation (projects are funded on equal footing) ²	Focuses on relatively low-risk technologies with no need for risk absorption.
Risk absorption (reduce large TRL gap)	Public seed funding to foster ideas with breakthrough potential (100k EUR). ATTRACT2 aims to continue with public scale funding for selected projects (2-4M EUR).		
Risk mitigation (close TRL gap)	Public/private investment mechanisms. ³	Public/private investment mechanisms.	Angel, Venture capital funding.
Pre-competitive market	Ensured in projects with participation of research infrastructures.	Not ensured and depending on a project-by-project case.	Not ensured.
Scaling up	Late-stage VC funding instruments, private equity, IPOs, etc.		

¹We are referring to EU funding programs such as Horizon 2020. We do not consider national public funding programs.

²Exceptions exist, such as the SME instrument <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/smeinstrument>. Nevertheless, they differ from ATTRACT because a project needs to apply for seed funding, and subsequently, for scale funding. In ATTRACT, the transition between seed and scale is streamlined.

³<http://www.eif.org/>; <http://www.eib.org/en/index.htm>

4.3 The 170 Funded ATTRACT Projects

The call was open from 1 August to 31 October 2018. In that period, 1,211 proposals were received. The top 10 countries submitting applications were as follows: Italy (261); Spain (230); Switzerland (108); France (96); the United Kingdom (81); Germany (67); Finland (65); the Netherlands (59); Portugal (33); and Austria (26). From these submissions, 170 projects were selected for funding.

To analyze these different projects, we carried out the following: We collected the text proposal of the 170 funded projects for analysis. Each proposal submitted contained a maximum of 3,000 words, including the following parts: a) summary; b) project description; c) technology description and external benchmarks; d) envisioned innovation potential (scientific and/or industrial), as well as envisioned social value; e) project implementation, budget, deliverables, and dissemination plan. The proposals of these 170 funded projects were read by the authors and three master's students for evaluation.

Three master's students with backgrounds in biomedical engineering, mechanical engineering/physics and entrepreneurship evaluated each project independently. They coded for the following project characteristics: technology readiness level (scale of 1 to 9), scope of market application (specific, specific but easily expandable, or general), location in the value chain (upstream or downstream), technology novelty (scale of 1 to 5), technology relevance to the market (scale of 1 to 5) and credibility of budget and milestones (scale of 1 to 5).

After analyzing each project separately, their findings were integrated. In cases where the codes were not consistent, discussions were held to reach agreement. The coding was then validated in an additional round of coding by the authors and then tabulated. As such, each project was evaluated and coded by a minimum of three independent evaluators. The results are presented in the following paragraphs.

The ATTRACT project call required the participation of a minimum of two collaborating organizations. While the majority of projects were the result of two organizations collaborating, as many as five organizations can be seen collaborating in a single project (Figure 1A).

Figure 1. Summary of organizations Involved in ATTRACT projects.

Exploring the countries represented in each project funded in ATTRACT, Figure 1B shows that **the majority of projects involve collaborations between organizations located in the same country**. Such arrangements allow the partners to closely interact and meet frequently as they work on their projects. Interestingly, almost half of the projects (45%) involve international collaboration. Especially when projects require highly specialized, scarcely available expertise among partners, it is necessary for collaborations to occur across borders.

The automated classification was, however, not adequate to fully understand the projects included within ATTRACT. We, thus, conduct further analyses by manually evaluating the textual data of the projects. Figure 3A shows the different technological domains as submitted the participants, which are as follows: sensors (70%), data-acquisition systems and computing (32%), software and integration (30%) and front and back-end electronics (16%). Note that the projects can belong to more than one domain so they do not add up to exactly 100%. As observed, a large percentage of projects are in the domain of sensors. This percentage is not unexpected, as big science infrastructures are generally known for the sophistication of their imaging and detection technologies. The high expertise of these groups in sensor technology, together with the versatility of sensors towards various uses, make them good candidates for exploring alternative commercial applications.

Figure 3. Summary of the Various Coded Dimensions of the ATTRACT Projects.

Further analysis was carried out to describe the different features of the funded projects under ATTRACT (Figure 3). Figure 3B shows that **ATTRACT caters to a diverse range of application areas, including healthcare (36%), electronics (20%), environment (12%), energy (6%), security (6%) and manufacturing (6%)**. These projects commit to these areas in varying degrees. Figure 3C shows that the projects are almost equally split in terms of the degree of specificity in the application area. While 35% of the projects are specific to their mentioned application area, there are also a large number of projects offering a general solution to different application areas (28%).

An interesting category is the 38% that are specific but expandable projects that have already identified their pilot market but then can easily extend their reach to other areas.

Furthermore, Figure 3D shows that there are slightly more projects located upstream in the value chain. These upstream projects (55%) aim to supply companies with knowledge and technologies that can be further processed and integrated towards their offerings. In contrast, downstream projects (45%) cater directly towards solving the problems of its intended market.

Figure 3E shows that the most common technology readiness level was 2, meaning that the projects are only in the stage where the technology and/or application area has been conceptualized. The average TRL across all projects was 1.8. These low TRL values are in line with what was expected from the projects during the proposal call. The low TRLs show that **these technologies are still in their early stages, requiring further development towards becoming viable solutions**. Their low TRLs have the benefit, however, of giving them the flexibility to find the serendipitous area where their application will have the most impact.

Originating from the leading big science infrastructures, the projects feature some of the most advanced, cutting-edge technologies

Originating from the leading big science infrastructures, the projects feature some of the most advanced, cutting-edge technologies. Figure 3F shows that **the projects are highly novel, with an average rating of 3.4 out of 5**. The problem typically with technologies that are too novel is finding areas that would be relevant for their application. However, as seen in Figure 3G, the projects have generally high relevance to the markets they are hoping to serve. Across all projects, the average rating was 3.5 out of 5. This rating implies that a project such as ATTRACT can help activate researchers to find relevant applications for the technologies they are working on. Otherwise, for projects lower in rating, the support provided by ATTRACT enables these projects to refine their technologies to find a better fit with their market of choice or to find a more applicable market to which their solutions can be of value.

A project such as ATTRACT can help activate researchers to find relevant applications for the technologies they are working on

To systematically explore the space in the development of their technologies, it is important for the project's team to have a credible plan and list of milestones. Figure 3H shows that the projects were rated highly on this aspect, with an average rating of 3.5 out of 5.

4.4 Modes towards serendipity

In the project text, the researchers typically narrate the mode by which they were able to develop new applications for their scientific research. We identified the recurrent themes by which serendipitous discoveries were actively pursued by project members in our first read through the 170 projects. In the second and third readings, we categorized the projects according to the following criteria:

- **Combination of different technologies** – technologies or knowledge from different research domains is combined, integrated or assembled together to produce a new application.
- **Building on previous research** – technologies from previous research work are extended or improved to be more effective or efficient but are still within the same domain or application area.
- **Applying technology to another field** – technology or knowledge from one domain is used in a new research domain or application area.
- **Using machine learning or artificial intelligence** – when the computational advances in machine learning or artificial intelligence are used to augment or find new uses for existing technologies.

Note that the projects typically combine these modes to different degrees and so, we coded them according to what is explicitly mentioned in the text. The number of projects in each category is summarized in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Modes towards serendipity in the ATTRACT projects

4.4.1 Combination of different technologies

The most represented mode was the combination of different technologies (41%). Under this category, technologies could come from adjacent or distant domains. Moreover, these technologies could be combined with varying degrees of integration. On one extreme, we identify a subset of projects (16%) where existing, readily available technologies are assembled to develop a new application. For instance, a project called PHIL, which aims to use a photonic system for liquid biopsy, mentions the following:

“We will design and build the system using mainly commercial solutions for the different system aspects.”

Otherwise, many projects combine the latest advances from distant research areas to create novel solutions. A notable example is the SCENT project, which aims to create new gas sensors. The project mentions that it is:

“based on merging two up-to-now disjointed macro-disciplines: high-pressure technology and gas-sensing; whose scientific communities are still far one another: the former focusing mainly on synthesis of materials, the latter unaware of HP-potentialities.”

4.4.2 Building on previous research

The second mode we identified is extending and building on previous research (31%). Typically, this mode proceeds from re-examining previous research so that new features that have not been previously identified or explored can surface. Pursuing this re-examination typically requires a meticulous re-examination of previously acquired knowledge and finding new perspectives in the existing data. A notable example is the project Random Power, which is a random bit generator for cryptography. According to their proposal:

“The genesis of the project is an example of ingenuity and serendipity and can be tracked to the effort of understanding random events affecting the response of state-of-the-art detectors of light with single-photon sensitivity.”

Another way that previous research is reinterpreted is by exaggerating features or taking things to the extreme. For instance, there are many projects that examine what possibilities would be opened if current detectors could be applied at extremely cold temperatures or in environments with very high radiation. Similarly, there are projects that develop new application areas through imagining what opportunities can be created if a technology becomes a magnitude more efficient or powerful.

The previous research can also be extended by projecting from the current state of their research a laudable target. By setting a difficult goal, the researchers then leave it to their abilities and to successful development of the project so that they can bridge the gap between this goal and their current state.

4.4.3 Applying technology to another field

Another set of projects (27%) applied a technology from one field to another field. This category coincides best with the previous notions of serendipity – finding new uses from existing things. By exposing a technology to a field that it has not been previously used for, new use cases for the technology potentially emerge. Especially for the big science institutes in ATTRACT, their technologies might be narrowly used within their scientific domain. These new technologies are also able to provide a fresh perspective to the field, proposing new ways to deal with the problems that the existing technologies currently employed within the field may not adequately address.

By exposing a technology to a field that it has not been previously used for, new use cases for the technology potentially emerge

A notable example of a project is SIMS, which involves designing a seismic imaging and monitoring system. They mention that they will develop a:

“next-generation MEMS sensor that utilizes patented technology inspired by the search for gravitational waves.”

4.4.4 Using artificial intelligence or machine learning

The final mode we identified involved the application of machine learning for a specific application, accounting for 14% of the projects. This category can be considered a subset of the previous category since machine learning is a breakthrough originating from the computational sciences that is finding new uses in different domains. By being able to find patterns that humans cannot easily identify, it can be said that **applying AI or machine learning increases the efficacy of various sensors** in what can be obtained from the data it is able to collect.

Many of the projects in this category are in the field of healthcare. The usage of machine learning **allows data collected from the various imaging technologies to be brought together and processed to reveal new insights on certain diseases**. For instance, the project MAGres plans to integrate various magnetic resonance techniques to obtain a better understanding of the brain tumor glioblastoma. They mention the following:

“ML (machine learning) methods are the key to unlock the predictive power from the complex and high-dimensional data to be acquired.”

5. Discussion

We identify four categories of how big science research can be used in previously unexplored ways towards commercial applications. These four modes towards serendipity are (1) a combination of different technologies, (2) building on previous research, (3) applying technology to another field and (4) using AI or machine learning. Compared to the previous studies of serendipity, the categories we describe do not completely coincide with any one proposed typology of serendipity, as summarized in Table 2.

CULTIVATING SERENDIPITY		SERENDIPITY VIEWED FROM ITS OUTCOME		OTHER LITERATURE ON SERENDIPITY
Categories from ATTRACT (This Article)	Structure of Serendipity (de Rond, 2014)	Typology of Serendipity (Yaqub 2018)	Exaptation of Science-based Innovation (Garud 2018)	
Applying a technology to another field	<hr/> Serendipity by way of random variation <hr/> Serendipity as the unintended consequence of design	Walpolian targeted search solves an unexpected problem	Franklin's character was previously shaped for some use but is now coopted for a different role (ex. coin as screwdriver)	
Building on previous research	<hr/> Pseudo-serendipity by way of random variation <hr/> Pseudo-serendipity as the unintended consequence of design	Mertonian targeted search solves problem via an unexpected route		
Combining together different technologies				Crossovers between components (Fink <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Applying AI/Machine learning				Computer-aided serendipity (Arvo, 1999)
Untargeted search (during research before ATTRACT)		<hr/> Bushian untargeted search solves an immediate problem <hr/> Stephanian untargeted search solves a problem later	<hr/> Milton's character was not shaped for some use but has the potential to be coopted for another use (ex. spandrels)	

The category of applying technology from one field to another coincides highly with the previous notions of Walpolian serendipity (Yaqub, 2018) and the idea of exaptation (Garud *et al.*, 2018). These two formulations, on a fundamental level, refer to the unanticipated usage of a certain item. A nuanced difference, however, between these previous notions on serendipity is that our categorization stems from a different view of serendipity, i.e., exploring the modes towards its realization. Instead of characterizing it ex-ante, our category describes the actions that researchers are actually taking in the hopes of finding serendipitous applications for their scientific research.

On the surface, extending the previous research does not seem to be related to serendipity. The implied incremental nature of the progress that comes from building on previous research makes it seem that it is not a viable way to cultivate serendipity. However, as we find in the different projects, **extending the previous research can be productive, especially if it allows the accumulated wealth of knowledge and experience of various actors to be activated and re-examined.** This productivity coincides with how Cunha *et al.*, (2010) sees serendipity, i.e., as the process of metaphorical association – seeing things in a new way. Such activation facilitates researchers to pursue a laudable target that they have not considered doing before.

Compared to the previous typologies of serendipity, we find two new categories. The first one is the combination of different technologies. This conceptualization of the phenomenon is consistent with that of Fink *et al.* (2017), which relates serendipity to the surprise from the crossover of interdependent components. On a fundamental level, the innovation research has greatly emphasized the role of combining knowledge from diverse domains to generate breakthrough innovation (e.g., Guan and Yan, 2016; Schoenmakers and Duysters, 2010). Nonetheless, it has not been explicitly linked to serendipity due to the lack of empirical studies on its realization.

Finally, in the ATTRACT projects on AI and machine learning were used to process and make sense of the huge quantities of data generated by the various sensors. **These technologies are valuable, as they are able to see subtle patterns that are invisible to the human eye.** AI and machine learning improve the performance of certain technologies by being able to process large amounts of data and integrate different sources of information to obtain new insights. However, it is important to make a distinction that AI and machine learning were mainly used to integrate the data resulting from the detectors instead of for discovering new applications. Machine learning was not used on a meta-level to discover new serendipitous applications of the technologies, for instance, from mining text from publications and patents. However, with the ongoing progress in these technologies (as in recommender systems), it would be interesting to see how AI and machine learning can directly be used to generate leads for serendipitous connections between various topics (e.g., Arvo, 1999; Giles and Walkowicz, 2019).

5.1 Implications for theory

The research on serendipity has evolved beyond the simple conceptualization as an accident or happenstance. Recent developments have allowed serendipity to be scientifically examined by having reformulated it as a capacity, requiring the focus of attention (de Rond, 2014). This paper validates the previously proposed typologies on serendipity through the unique dataset of ATTRACT. While the previous research on serendipity mainly relied on anecdotal stories in the history of science, ours is grounded on the data from the 170 funded projects under ATTRACT. With these projects spanning different domains and varying in their technological features, this gives us access to a large dataset that we can probe to study how serendipity is actively pursued.

While the previous research on serendipity mainly relied on anecdotal stories in the history of science, ours is grounded on the data from the 170 funded projects under ATTRACT

Unlike the previous studies of serendipity, which view the phenomenon after it has already occurred, we provide another perspective by looking at the modes towards its realization. **This process-oriented data-driven approach allowed us to find two previously unidentified modes wherein serendipity can be cultivated,** as follows: combining technologies and using machine learning. More systematic analyses with other novel datasets are needed to corroborate our findings and identify other means that serendipity can be realized.

5.2 Implications for policy and practice

Our paper shows how policy can enable researchers to find alternate serendipitous uses for their technologies. The ATTRACT project is consistent with calls by Mazzucato (2013, 2016, 2017), who argues that **the government can go beyond its role as a regulator or fixer of markets towards an entrepreneurial role, absorbing the risks in strategic sectors until technologies have reached a sufficiently mature state** to be attractive to private and venture capital.

Market mechanisms and private capital alone may not be the most efficient routes to realizing innovation via basic to applied research

This assumes that market mechanisms and private capital alone may not be the most efficient routes to realizing innovation via basic to applied research (Martin, 2016). Specific industrial policies and stimulus instruments are needed to absorb the risks in basic research settings when working with low TRL technologies. This is particularly relevant to ATTRACT in light of the empirical research suggesting that the more the research infrastructure is involved in basic research as part of its mission, the less likely that the organization will be involved in technology transfer activities (Boisot *et al.*, 2011; Rahm *et al.*, 1988); this is certainly the case for several ATTRACT partners.

ATTRACT also resonates with the 'cooperative technology' model of technology transfer described by Bozeman (2000), which assumes that **government laboratories and research infrastructures can play an important role in technology innovation and economic growth**. With some variation, authors such as Mazzucato and Bozeman echo the original doctrine of Vannevar Bush, i.e., that basic research has a substantial and positive impact on socio-economic innovation via direct and indirect mechanisms.

Interestingly, however, the recent literature has argued that while it is commonly believed that Bush maintained an unquestioning faith in an integrated and linear model of innovation, his notion was more sophisticated and involved symbiotic cross-fertilization (Leyden and Menter, 2018). In this view, the authors argue that while Bush saw that basic research and applied research benefit each other, they also succeed by working as separate systems, or stacks. Consequently, **scientific and economic policy mechanisms should seek to coordinate the two systems**, allowing each to operate through its own logic and success criteria, yet simultaneously cultivating specific points where they can nurture each other (Cunningham *et al.*, 2013; European Commission, 2016b; Leyden and Menter, 2018). ATTRACT does not presume to be the definitive word on how to accomplish this coordination task. Indeed, faithful to its genesis in scientific institutions, ATTRACT should be seen as an experiment in innovation policy (Bakhshi *et al.*, 2011). With its focus on the revelation of information and cross-fertilization of technology and entrepreneurial options, it is experimental at an operational level. With its novel constellation of actors, resources, design, and governance, ATTRACT is very much an experiment in innovation policy.

ATTRACT should be seen as an experiment in innovation policy

6. Conclusions

The 170 projects allow us to probe serendipity in a quasiexperimental setting with some controls

We have described the ATTRACT project, which is a novel innovation policy instrument to find new applications for the breakthrough imaging, detection, and computational technologies of Europe's leading scientific research infrastructures.

We have described the philosophy behind the project, discussing the history of big science and the issues with regard to assessing its socioeconomic impact. Where ATTRACT is still in-process, the large data set from the proposals allows us to view serendipity in a unique, unprecedented manner. Specifically, the 170 projects allow us to probe serendipity in a quasi-experimental setting with some controls. We identify several novel modalities of serendipity that emerge from the data.

There are many interesting avenues for future research. First, it is a widely accepted wisdom that **increasing the collisions between different actors promotes the chances of serendipity**. As such, it is valuable to understand how the various partners working in the projects were able to find each other and create new applications for their previous technologies. Incorporating insights from the alliance and network literature would create new insights in the serendipity literature.

Faithful to its genesis in scientific institutions, ATTRACT is best viewed as a policy experiment. Where a complete evaluation of it will require more time, the initial evidence suggests that **policymakers can play a purposeful and effective role in fostering derivative benefits from public investments in big scientific research infrastructures**.

7. Acknowledgments

ATTRACT has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 777222.

8. References

- Almirall, E., Wareham, J., 2011. Living Labs: Arbiters of midand ground-level innovation. *Technol. Anal. Strateg. Manag.* <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2011.537110>
- Arvo, J., 1999. Computer aided serendipity: the role of autonomous assistants in problem solving. *Proc. 1999 Conf. Graph. interface '99*.
- Aschhoff, B., Sofka, W., 2009. Innovation on demand—Can public procurement drive market success of innovations? *Res. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2009.06.011>
- Auerswald, P.E., Branscomb, L.M., 2003. Valleys of death and Darwinian seas: Financing the invention to innovation transition in the United States, in: *Journal of Technology Transfer.* <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1024980525678>
- Autio, E., Hameri, A.-P., Bianchi-Streit, M., 2003. Technology transfer and technological learning through CERN's procurement activity. CERN.
- Autio, E., Hameri, A.P., Nordberg, M., 1996. A framework of motivations for industry - Big science collaboration: A case study. *J. Eng. Technol. Manag. - JET-M.* [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0923-4748\(96\)01011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0923-4748(96)01011-9)
- Autio, E., Hameri, A.P., Vuola, O., 2004. A framework of industrial knowledge spillovers in big-science centers. *Res. Policy.* [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(03\)00105-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(03)00105-7)
- Bahar, S., 2018. Spandrels, Exaptations, and Raw Material. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-024-1054-9_15
- Bakhshi, H., Freeman, A., Potts, J., 2011. State of Uncertainty: Innovation policy through experimentation. Nesta.
- Banke, J., 2010. Technology readiness levels demystified [WWW Document]. *Natl. Aeronaut. Sp. Adm.* URL https://www.nasa.gov/topics/aeronautics/features/trl_demystified.html
- Beale, R., 2007. Supporting serendipity: Using ambient intelligence to augment user exploration for data mining and web browsing. *Int. J. Hum. Comput. Stud.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2006.11.012>
- Beard, T.R., Ford, G.S., Koutsky, T.M., Spiwak, L.J., 2009. A Valley of Death in the innovation sequence: an economic investigation. *Res. Eval.* 18, 343–356. <https://doi.org/10.3152/095820209X481057>
- Bianco, W., Gerhart, D., Nicolson-Crotty, S., 2017. Waypoints for Evaluating Big Science*. *Soc. Sci. Q.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/ssqu.12467>
- Boisot, M., Nordberg, M., Yami, S., Nicquevert, B., 2011. *Collisions and Collaboration: The Organization of Learning in the ATLAS Experiment at the LHC.* Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199567928.001.0001>
- Borrás, S., Edquist, C., 2013. The choice of innovation policy instruments. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2013.03.002>
- Borrás, S., Laatsit, M., 2019. Towards system oriented innovation policy evaluation? Evidence from EU28 member states. *Res. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.08.020>
- Bush, V., 1945. *Science, the Endless Frontier: A Report to the President by Vanevar Bush, Director of the Office of Scientific Research and Development.* July 1945. US Gov. Print. Off. Washingt. 1945.
- Butler, D., 2008. Translational research: Crossing the valley of death. *Nature.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/453840a>
- Castelnuovo, P., Florio, M., Forte, S., Rossi, L., Sirtori, E., 2018. The economic impact of technological procurement for large-scale research infrastructures: Evidence from the Large Hadron Collider at CERN. *Res. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.06.018>
- Chesbrough, H.W., 2003. *Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology.*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8691.2008.00502.x>
- Corneli, J., Jordanous, A., Guckelsberger, C., Pease, A., Colton, S., 2014. Modelling serendipity in a computational context. *arXiv Prepr. arXiv1411.0440.*
- Crease, R.P., Martin, J.D., Pesic, P., 2016. Megascience. *Phys. Perspect.* 18, 355–356. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00016-016-0193-0>

- Cunha, M.P.e., Clegg, S.R., Mendonça, S., 2010. On serendipity and organizing. *Eur. Manag. J.* 28, 319–330. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2010.07.001>
- Cunningham, P., Edler, J., Flanagan, K., Laredo, P., 2013. Innovation policy mix and instrument interaction: a review. Manchester Univ. Manchester.
- de Rond, M., 2014. The structure of serendipity. *Cult. Organ.* 20, 342–358. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14759551.2014.967451>
- Dew, N., 2009. Serendipity in Entrepreneurship. *Organ. Stud.* 30, 735–753. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840609104815>
- Doing, P., 2018. Velvet Revolution at the Synchrotron, Velvet Revolution at the Synchrotron. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/7537.001.0001>
- Edler, J., Fagerberg, J., 2017. Innovation policy: What, why, and how. *Oxford Rev. Econ. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/grx001>
- Edler, J., Georghiou, L., 2007. Public procurement and innovation-Resurrecting the demand side. *Res. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2007.03.003>
- European Commission, 2016a. Open innovation, open science, open to the world - a vision for Europe. <https://doi.org/10.2777/552370>
- European Commission, 2016b. Supply and Demand Side Innovation Policies.
- European Commission, 2012. Commission Recommendation of 17.7.2012 on access to and preservation of scientific information.
- Fink, T.M.A., Reeves, M., Palma, R., Farr, R.S., 2017. Serendipity and strategy in rapid innovation. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-02042-w>
- Florio, M., Forte, S., Sirtori, E., 2016. Forecasting the socio-economic impact of the Large Hadron Collider: A cost-benefit analysis to 2025 and beyond. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.03.007>
- Florio, M., Sirtori, E., 2016. Social benefits and costs of large scale research infrastructures. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2015.11.024>
- Frank, C., Sink, C., Mynatt, L., Rogers, R., Rappazzo, A., 1996. Surviving the valley of death: A comparative analysis. *J. Technol. Transf.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02220308>
- Frost & Sullivan, 2015. 2015 Top Technologies in Sensors & Control (Technical Insights).
- Galison, P., 2016. Meanings of scientific unity: The law, the orchestra, the pyramid, the quilt and the ring, in: Pursuing the Unity of Science. Routledge, pp. 12–29.
- Galison, P., Hevly, B., 1992. Big Science: The Growth of Large-Scale Research. Stanford University Press.
- Garud, R., Gehman, J., Giuliani, A.P., 2018. Serendipity arrangements for exapting science-based innovations. *Acad. Manag. Perspect.* <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2016.0138>
- Giles, D., Walkowicz, L., 2019. Systematic serendipity: A test of unsupervised machine learning as a method for anomaly detection. *Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty3461>
- Giudice, G.F., 2012. Big Science and the Large Hadron Collider. *Phys. Perspect.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00016-011-0078-1>
- Guan, J.C., Yan, Y., 2016. Technological proximity and recombinative innovation in the alternative energy field. *Res. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2016.05.002>
- Hallonsten, O., 2014. How expensive is Big Science? Consequences of using simple publication counts in performance assessment of large scientific facilities. *Scientometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1249-z>
- Hammett, F.S., 1941. The "meaning" of science. *Science* (80-). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.93.2425.595-a>
- Héder, M., 2017. From NASA to EU: The evolution of the TRL scale in Public Sector Innovation. *Innov. J.*
- Heidler, R., Hallonsten, O., 2015. Qualifying the performance evaluation of Big Science beyond productivity, impact and costs. *Scientometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-015-1577-7>
- Heinze, T., Hallonsten, O., 2017. The reinvention of the SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory, 1992–2012. *Hist. Technol.* 33, 300–332. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07341512.2018.1449711>

- Hellström, T., Jacob, M., 2012. Revisiting "Weinberg's Choice": Classic Tensions in the Concept of Scientific Merit. *Minerva*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-012-9203-9>
- Hiltzik, M., 2016. *Big Science: Ernest Lawrence and the Invention that Launched the Military-Industrial Complex*. Simon & Schuster.
- Hudson, J., Khazragui, H.F., 2013. Into the valley of death: Research to innovation. *Drug Discov. Today*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2013.01.012>
- Islam, N., 2017. Crossing the Valley of Death-An Integrated Framework and a Value Chain for Emerging Technologies. *IEEE Trans. Eng. Manag.* <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2017.2685138>
- Kotkov, D., Wang, S., Veijalainen, J., 2016. A survey of serendipity in recommender systems. *Knowledge-Based Syst.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2016.08.014>
- Leyden, D.P., Menter, M., 2018. The legacy and promise of Vannevar Bush: rethinking the model of innovation and the role of public policy. *Econ. Innov. New Technol.* <https://doi.org/10.1080/10438599.2017.1329189>
- Lundvall, B.Å., 2010. National systems of Innovation: Toward a theory of Innovation and Interactive Learning. *National Systems of Innovation: Toward a Theory of Innovation and Interactive Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.7135/UPO9781843318903>
- Lundvall, B.A., Borrás, S., 2009. Science, Technology, and Innovation Policy, in: *The Oxford Handbook of Innovation*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199286805.003.0022>
- Mak, K.K., Pichika, M.R., 2019. Artificial intelligence in drug development: present status and future prospects. *Drug Discov. Today*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2018.11.014>
- Makri, S., Blandford, A., Woods, M., Sharples, S., Maxwell, D., 2014. "Making my own luck": Serendipity strategies and how to support them in digital information environments. *J. Assoc. Inf. Sci. Technol.* 65, 2179–2194. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23200>
- Markham, S.K., Ward, S.J., Aiman-Smith, L., Kingon, A.I., 2010. The valley of death as context for role theory in product innovation. *J. Prod. Innov. Manag.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5885.2010.00724.x>
- Martin, B.R., 2016. Twenty challenges for innovation studies. *Sci. Public Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scv077>
- Mazzucato, M., 2016. From market fixing to market-creating: a new framework for innovation policy. *Ind. Innov.* <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2016.1146124>
- Mazzucato, M., Semieniuk, G., 2017. Public financing of innovation: New questions. *Oxford Rev. Econ. Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/grw036>
- McCay-Peet, L., Toms, E.G., 2015. Investigating serendipity: How it unfolds and what may influence it. *J. Assoc. Inf. Sci. Technol.* 66, 1463–1476. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23273>
- Merriam-Webster, 2020. Serendipity [WWW Document]. Merriam-Webster.com Dict. URL <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/serendipity> (accessed 2.25.20).
- Merton, R.K., Barber, E., 2004. *The travels and adventures of serendipity: A study in sociological semantics and the sociology of science*. Princeton University Press.
- Mowery, D.C., 2012. Defense-related R&D as a model for "grand Challenges" technology policies. *Res. Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2012.03.027>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2014. *The Impacts of Large Research Infrastructures on Economic Innovation and on Society: Case Studies at CERN*.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), 2003. *Turning Science into Business: Patenting and Licensing at Public Research Organisations*.
- Oxford University Press, 2019. Serendipity [WWW Document]. Lexico.com. URL <https://www.lexico.com/definition/serendipity> (accessed 2.25.20).
- Rahm, D., Bozeman, B., Crow, M., 1988. Domestic Technology Transfer and Competitiveness: An Empirical Assessment of Roles of University and Governmental R&D Laboratories. *Public Adm. Rev.* <https://doi.org/10.2307/976993>
- Rolfstam, M., 2009. Public procurement as an innovation policy tool: The role of institutions. *Sci. Public Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.3152/030234209X442025>
- Rosenman, M.F., 2001. Serendipity and Scientific Discovery, in: *Creativity and Leadership in the 21st Century*. pp. 187–193.

Scherer, F.M., 1982. Demand-Pull and Technological Invention: Schmookler Revisted. *J. Ind. Econ.* <https://doi.org/10.2307/2098216>

Schmookler, J., 1962. Economic Sources of Inventive Activity. *J. Econ. Hist.* <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022050700102311>

Schoenmakers, W., Duysters, G., 2010. The technological origins of radical inventions. *Res. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2010.05.013>

Schopper, H., 2016. Some remarks concerning the cost/benefit analysis applied to LHC at CERN. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 112, 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.02.007>

Scudellari, M., 2017. Big science has a buzzword problem. *Nature.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/541450a>

Weinberg, A.M., 1964. Criteria for scientific choice II: The two cultures. *Minerva.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01630147>